

**Synaesthesia as a Model for Assessing Individual Differences in Visual Perception and
Memory Performance**

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Author Note and Contributions

The study data and materials will be shared openly as part of the publication of the article. The proposed protocol has been reviewed and accepted by the ethics committee of the University of Sussex (ref. ER/JAMIEW/30). The study has received financial support from the Swiss National Science Foundation (ref. 204314). The authors have no competing financial interests to declare.

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Abstract

Memory and perception may utilise common neurocognitive resources (such that more precise perception drives more robust memories), rather than being entirely separate cognitive domains as traditionally believed. This study explores this claim by adopting an individual differences approach using synaesthesia as a test case. Synaesthesia has been linked to both enhanced memory and perception but the relationship between these observations is unclear due to inconsistent methodologies for measuring memory and perception (not amenable to direct comparison) and the presence of potential confounds (e.g., cognitive styles) that may act as a latent variable in driving associations. We compared visual perceptual precision (for colour and location) and short- and long-term memory performance across three groups: synaesthetes ($N = 115$), non-synaesthetic first-degree relatives of synaesthetes ($N = 80$), and non-synaesthetic unrelated controls ($N = 109$).

Synaesthetes showed clear advantages compared to both non-synaesthetic first-degree relatives and unrelated controls in all visual perception and memory tasks. Consistent with a shared cognitive resource, regression analyses indicated that memory advantages were largely mediated by perceptual precision, rather than by synaesthesia status, vividness of mental imagery or intrinsic motivation. Grapheme-colour synaesthesia conferred advantages across almost all tasks and conditions (particularly when colour was the dependent variable). Sequence-space synaesthesia was also linked to enhanced performance in perception and memory but with no specific advantage for location over colour. First degree relatives did not show the same advantages as synaesthetes.

These findings support the enhanced processing account of synaesthesia, highlighting perceptual precision as a key mediator of memory differences associated with synaesthesia.

Keywords: Perception, memory, synaesthesia, endophenotype

Deleted: In this study, the cognitive profile of synaesthesia (a perceptual condition in which primary experiences, such as perceiving digits or words, elicit extra secondary sensations) is used as a model system to assess visual perceptual abilities and memory performance in the general population. Synaesthesia serves as a suitable framework for examining variations in visual perception and visual memory among individuals, as it has been associated with visual perception and memory advantages. We compare the cognitive profile of three groups: synaesthetes, non-synaesthetic relatives of synaesthetes, and non-synaesthetic non-relative controls. We use measures of visual perception and performance on short and long-term memory tasks with colour and location manipulations to derive a detailed and multivariate profile of each group. A key strength of our approach is that perception and memory tasks are perfectly matched in terms of generating the same dependent variable. We also assess mental imagery, cognitive style, and motivation using questionnaires. We expect our work to further develop theories on the relationship between perceptual ability and memory performance and to elucidate whether synaesthesia is epiphenomenal or functionally related to different or enhanced cognitive processes.¶

1. Introduction

Individual differences research in cognitive psychology seeks to understand how people use cognitive mechanisms in different ways to perform the same task. It aims to explain why some participants systematically differ from the aggregate data pattern, for reasons other than statistical noise (Logie, 2018). Recent attempts to develop predictive models of brain-behaviour relationships have shown that, whilst successful for most people, there are subgroups within the general population who are consistently hard to fit (Greene et al., 2022). One group that tends to deviate from the norm in terms of their cognitive profile is people with synaesthesia. Synaesthesia is a perceptual trait in which primary experiences, such as perceiving digits or words, elicit extra secondary sensations (Simner, 2012; Simner & Hubbard, 2013; Ward, 2013; Ward & Simner, 2020). Synaesthesia is an appropriate model system to test individual differences in visual perception and visual memory because these individuals are a largely hidden subgroup within the neurotypical population (it is not a disorder) with known differences in cognition, for example displaying enhanced visual acuity (e.g., Banissy et al., 2009, 2013; Barnett et al., 2008) and memory abilities (e.g., Lunke & Meier, 2018; Ovalle-Fresa, Ankner, et al., 2021; Rothen et al., 2012; Rothen & Meier, 2010). Here we take this an important step further by determining the extent to which individual differences relating to perception and memory are related (i.e., such that variation in one explains variation in the other). We utilise people with and without synaesthesia as a 'natural experiment' of cognitive variation to determine the extent to which individual differences in perception and memory co-occur within the same visual characteristics, also noting that synaesthetes have a heterogeneous presentation (e.g., varying in whether synaesthetic experiences involve colour or spatial experiences or not). This allows us to examine differences amongst synaesthetes as a secondary question.

Historically, perception and memory are considered largely separable domains of cognition (e.g., Marr & Brindley, 1997; Ranganath & Ritchey, 2012). However, tests of perception and memory are typically not matched in terms of either stimulus properties or task demands. When they are more closely matched, similarities between perception and memory can be found in terms of both neural

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substrates and behaviour (e.g., Graham et al., 2010; Rothen et al., 2012). Research including individuals with other specific conditions affecting perception, memory, and mental imagery, also suggests a closer link between these cognitive processes than previously thought. In cases of amnesia difficulties in both perception and memory are apparent when using similar stimuli, such as scenes (Barense et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2005). People with aphantasia (who lack visual mental imagery) show slower response times to equivalent tasks both when perceiving and imagining from memory (Liu & Bartolomeo, 2023).

Here, to further probe the link between perception and memory, we use a delayed estimation (continuous report) paradigm that can be adapted as a fair test across putatively different cognitive domains (perception, short-term, and long-term memory) and visual characteristics (colour, location) (see Brady et al., 2013; Fan et al., 2016; Ovalle-Fresa, Ankner, et al., 2021; Schurgin, 2018 for similar paradigms). To measure how perception and memory performance may vary according to individual differences in the vividness of visual mental imagery and cognitive style, we use questionnaires to capture differences between select healthy special populations: synaesthetes, their non-synaesthetic relatives and controls. In doing so, we can contribute evidence to debates regarding the modularity and structure of cognitive systems in the brain (including differences in the processing of spatial and colour object features) and can also examine the extent and magnitude to which differences in perception and memory exist in the general population, rather than in extreme cases like amnesia.

Synaesthesia consists of two fundamental elements: the presence of a stimuli that triggers the synaesthetic experience (the “inducer”) and the synaesthetic experience itself (the “concurrent”) (Grossenbacher & Lovelace, 2001). Here we focus on two of the most common types, namely grapheme-colour synaesthesia (where language units such as graphemes or words trigger colour sensations) and sequence-space synaesthesia (where numbers or other ordered sequences are experienced as if they were points in space) (Ward & Simner, 2022). In terms of cognitive differences, it is generally observed that people with synaesthesia display enhanced visual perceptual

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sensitivity for colour information, report richer mental imagery, and an enhanced memory performance as compared to controls (Banissy et al., 2013; Barnett & Newell, 2008; Lunke & Meier, 2018; Rothen & Meier, 2010). Some studies show that memory advantages are specific to grapheme-colour synaesthesia and absent from sequence-space synaesthesia (Lunke & Meier, 2020), while others do not show a difference between synaesthesia types (Rothen et al., 2012). As such, it remains debatable whether the cognitive differences linked to synaesthesia occur irrespective of how it is manifested, in terms of inducer-concurrent pairings, or not (noting that these are not mutually exclusive options). These are also linked to different theoretical accounts.

There are two main theoretical accounts of cognitive differences in synaesthesia which predict a link between the nature of the memoranda and the profile of enhanced memory in synaesthesia: the “dual-coding” and “enhanced processing” accounts. In the dual-coding account of synaesthesia, the synaesthetic experience is understood to enhance memory performance by making available to synaesthetes additional retrieval cues in memory representations (Ghirardelli di Set et al., 2010; Smilek et al., 2005). Specifically, performance advantages are perceived to manifest for verbal material due to additional encoding as a mental image (Paivio et al., 1969). However, not all results fit with this account. For example, while Radvansky et al. (2011) found superior letter-spans but not number-spans in a group of letter-colour synaesthetes (evidence for dual-coding), other results directly testing the dual-coding account have not found a verbal advantage for synaesthetes with coloured letters but not numbers. Superior performers included synaesthetes with coloured numbers only (Smees et al., 2019). Some evidence also suggests that synaesthetes tend to have better visual memory (e.g., for colour and abstract fractal patterns) than verbal memory (Ward et al., 2013) and that grapheme-colour synaesthetes tend to think more visually and seem to rely less on semantic connotations (Radvansky et al., 2011). This suggests that advantages go beyond improved memory from dual-coding alone and indicates that some element of memory is atypically sensitive in this group, rather than the synaesthetic experiences manifesting from a typically functioning memory system.

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In the 'enhanced processing' account of synaesthesia, a central premise is that there are fundamental differences in the efficiency of some component of the memory system in synaesthetes that are not directly linked to synaesthetic experiences (Banissy et al., 2009; Baron-Cohen et al., 1993, 1996; Lunke & Meier, 2020; Rothen et al., 2012). For example, having enhanced memory for colour in general (e.g., remembering the colour of someone's clothes) rather than having colour as an extra experience (e.g., remembering someone's name by its synaesthetic colour). Here, wider changes in the visual system of synaesthetes are understood to give rise to a memory advantage, in addition to enhancements in certain perceptual abilities. The idea that individual differences in perception and memory are causally associated (for the same kind of memoranda) sits within a broader literature postulating a view of brain organisation in which regions are optimised for processing certain kinds of information (e.g., object versus location) but shared across all kinds of cognitive processes such as perception imagery, short- and long-term memory (e.g., Graham et al., 2010). This representational view of memory and perception does not rely on distinctions between different memory systems but emphasises the characteristics of the represented information, from simple features (e.g., colour) in early visual areas to feature conjunctions (e.g., individual objects) to conjunctions of feature conjunctions (i.e., complex visual scenes) in the hippocampus, at the endpoint of the visual ventral stream. Evidence for this account comes from studies on animals and brain-damaged patients (Cowell et al., 2010, 2019; Graham et al., 2010; Saksida, 2009), as well as neuroimaging and psychophysics results (Gardette et al., 2022; Kent et al., 2016). Evidence from grapheme-colour synaesthesia suggests enhanced functioning of the visual ventral stream in terms of greater EEG visual-evoked potentials to stimuli that preferentially engage it (e.g., Barnett et al., 2008), psychophysical evidence of enhanced colour and shape perception (Rothen et al., 2018), and better visual memory for shape and colour (Lunke & Meier, 2018; Pritchard et al., 2013; Terhune et al., 2013).

The extent to which different types of synaesthesia are linked to different profiles of enhanced processing is unclear. In grapheme-colour synaesthesia, several studies have shown that enhanced memory does not reliably extend to remembering the location of objects (Rothen & Meier, 2010; Yaro & Ward, 2018; Pritchard et al., 2013), a cognitive ability that might be expected to lie

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with the dorsal 'where' stream (e.g., Mishkin et al., 1983). A largely untested hypothesis is that synaesthetes with spatial concurrents (i.e., sequence-space synaesthesia) may show the complementary profile to grapheme-colour synaesthetes of enhanced processing of location rather than colour. That is, the manifestation of synaesthesia may be tied to relative enhancements of the visual ventral stream (favouring object and colour perception and memory in grapheme-colour synaesthesia) or visual dorsal stream (favouring location perception and memory in sequence-space synaesthesia). An alternative view is that there is an overarching cognitive profile linked to synaesthesia that is independent of its particular types but may, instead, be linked to synaesthesia per se. Certain questionnaires of cognitive style (e.g., attention-to-detail; Van Leeuwen et al., 2020; Van Leeuwen et al., 2021) and some multivariate test batteries (Ward & Filiz, 2020) extend to heterogeneous manifestations of synaesthesia (including the number of types that a person has). Of course, specific versus general cognitive differences need not be mutually exclusive: some individual differences in cognition may be linked to synaesthesia per se, and others to the specific type of synaesthesia.

These different accounts also make different predictions about the extent to which individual differences in cognition related to synaesthesia constitute an endophenotype; that is, first-degree relatives of synaesthetes may share these individual differences despite lacking synaesthesia. In the dual-coding account the prediction is that non-synaesthetic relatives would not show the same pattern because they lack synaesthesia and so cannot use it to their advantage. For the enhanced processing account, the predicted pattern would depend on whether enhanced processing acted as a cognitive disposition towards synaesthesia (in which case, one could have the disposition without developing synaesthesia) and whether that disposition was specific (to one type of synaesthesia) or general in nature. There is a genetic component to synaesthesia (Bargary & Mitchell, 2008; Fisher et al., 2019) and there is some evidence that it is generic in nature insofar as synaesthetic families contain members with different types (as opposed to some families having only grapheme-colour and others having only sequence-space). It is possible to have monozygotic twins where only one twin has synaesthesia (Bosley & Eagleman, 2015; Van Leeuwen et al., 2021; Smilek et al., 2005).

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However, the non-synaesthetic twin may still have individual differences that resemble that of a synaesthete. Using a machine learning classifier to discriminate synaesthetes from (unrelated) non-synaesthetes, based on their cognitive profile, it was found that related non-synaesthetes had an intermediate profile (Ward & Filiz, 2020). This is not a trivial finding of showing that genetically related people are cognitively similar but, instead, pairs of individuals from different families (and often on different continents) can be shown to be cognitively similar by virtue of having a first-degree relative with synaesthesia. Similarly, autism is found to co-occur not only within individuals with synaesthesia but amongst first-degree relatives who lack synaesthesia (Nugent & Ward, 2022).

The present study uses methods influenced by the earlier research of Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021), contrasting perception and memory with the same paradigm, and Ward and Filiz (2020) which examined the cognitive profile of non-synaesthetic relatives of synaesthetes. In Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) visual perceptual abilities and the accuracy of memory for colour was assessed across a visual perception task, a short-term memory task with load manipulations (either one, three or five images presented in various colours at once) and a long-term memory task where participants were asked to memorise object-colour associations. Results showed that grapheme-colour synaesthetes and colour experts share a common profile of enhanced visual perceptual ability and short-term memory in contrast to non-synaesthetic individuals from the more general population (there were no group differences in long-term memory and overall performance on that task was close to chance). A key strength of this approach is that perception and memory tasks are well matched in terms of generating the same dependent variable and being largely equivalent in terms of overall cognitive demands (aside from the ones of interest, such as passage of time). We measure the precision of perception and memory as a continuous variable rather than binary decisions (which necessarily entail some decision criteria). This study significantly expands the earlier study of Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) by comparing two different kinds of visual characteristics (colour, spatial location), including different kinds of synaesthesia, and considers whether these kinds of differences constitute an endophenotype present in the relatives of synaesthetes or are more directly related to the presence of synaesthesia per se. The long-term memory task has been changed to be easier

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by comprising several learning attempts over smaller blocks. We aim to determine the extent to which individual differences in memory and perception co-occur and, if so, whether they are material-specific, whether they depend on the specific manifestation of synaesthesia (involving colour or not) or depend on other individual differences that happen to be more common in synaesthesia (as an endophenotype).

1.1. Hypotheses

The hypotheses, sample rationale, analyses, and possible outcome interpretations are summarised in [the Supplementary Materials](#). The hypotheses are stated as follows:

[Hypothesis 1]. Synaesthetes will display enhanced visual perception and memory advantages relative to non-synaesthetes. Specifically, this should manifest itself as more precision in the choice of colours and locations across the tasks (perception, short-term memory, long-term memory).

[Hypothesis 2a]. Individual differences in performance on the perceptual task will predict performance on the memory tasks. Specifically, significant correlations should be observed between the precision of perception (of colour and location) and the corresponding visual characteristics when presented in equivalent short-term memory and long-term memory tasks.

[Hypothesis 2b, contingent on Hypotheses 2a]. The significant positive relationship between perception and memory will remain when synaesthesia status and other potential confounds (e.g., age, motivation, imagery) are included in a regression model.

[Hypothesis 3]. Grapheme-colour synaesthetes will have better memory and visual perceptual abilities for colour and sequence-space synaesthetes will have better memory and visual perceptual abilities for location, in comparison to each other and non-synaesthetic controls. Individuals with both types of synaesthesia will show advantages in both tasks.

[Hypothesis 4]. Relatives of synaesthetes will exhibit a similar pattern of visual perceptual ability and memory performance as the synaesthetes, albeit intermediate in magnitude. They will outperform non-synaesthetes who are not first-degree relatives of a synaesthete in the perception and memory tasks.

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2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Participants

Three groups were recruited: (1) participants with at least one type of synaesthesia (grapheme-colour and/or sequence-space) (2) first-degree non-synaesthetic relatives of synaesthetes and (3) non-synaesthetic non-related controls. Synaesthetes were recruited by means of our databases of synaesthetes who are willing to volunteer in experiments, synaesthesia groups on social media, word-of-mouth, and participant-pools at the UniDistance Suisse and the University of Sussex. Synaesthetes had passed the relevant tests of consistency, where high test-retest consistency was indicative of being a synaesthete. A mean score of < 135 in CIELUV colour space using the method of Rothen et al. (2013) was indicative of grapheme-colour synaesthesia. Where possible, within the grapheme-colour synaesthesia group, we prioritised recruitment of participants who reported colours for most letters and digits as this ensured a more robust assessment of synaesthesia. For sequence-space synaesthesia, we used the method of Ward et al. (2018) and a cut-off score of < -2 SD of randomly permuted consistency scores (Ward, 2022) plus a questionnaire score of < 19 . First-degree relatives were recruited via their synaesthetic relative. Controls were recruited through internet-based participants databases, such as Prolific.

2.1.1. Sample Size Determination

The study of Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) is the most similar to the current study in that it used the same paradigm albeit using colour only (not location). Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) reported group differences (synaesthetes versus non-synaesthetes) in visual perception of $d = 1.07$, and for the short-term memory task loads of one, three and five, had effect sizes of $d = .83, .64$ and $.37$ respectively (mean d for short-term memory of 0.61). As our hypothesis predicts a main effect of group for short-term memory we do not require significance at each and every load level and used the mean effect size for power calculations. Using G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) with a significance level (alpha) of 0.02 and power = 0.9, revealed that a minimum sample size of 61 per group would be required for a d of 0.61 (and be well powered for $d = 1.07$). We proposed an N of 100 for each of the synaesthete and control groups to allow for these effect sizes being overestimates and to

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allow for greater heterogeneity within the synaesthetes compared to earlier research which only used grapheme-colour synaesthetes. Recruiting non-synaesthetic relatives was likely to be more challenging and we set our limit at N=61, accounting for attrition across testing sessions. The data were to be analysed when these sample sizes had been reached. If the difference relating to relatives was non-significant and insensitive with N=61, we agreed to collect more data in batches of N=10 until the results were sensitive (Bayes), or a maximum sample of N=81 was reached. As expected, to meet the target range of N=61 to N=81 relatives, we continued recruitment of relatives after the N=100 target of synaesthetes was met (i.e., we tested 173 families to find 100 synaesthetes and 61-81 willing non-synaesthetic relatives).

Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) did not find a group difference in long-term memory but their task was very difficult with many participants performing at or near chance. Their version used a single learning block with a single large set of 40 associations. The task has been modified in the current study so that associations to 45 objects are learned over several smaller blocks (3 blocks of $n = 15$ objects) and with the addition of feedback after each trial (cf. also Ovalle-Fresa, Uslu, et al., 2021). The meta-analysis of Ward et al. (2019) reported a mean long-term memory effect size of $d = 0.61$, so the study is considered sufficiently powered to detect this. For our correlation analysis, taking a combined sample size (three groups) of $N = 261$ would be sufficient to detect a correlation coefficient of .13 with a power of 0.9 ($\alpha = .02$).

We note that the above power calculation is based on power for comparison of two independent means. This is because no prior research as to the effect sizes for comparison between synaesthetes and their relatives exists. However, if the difference between synaesthetes and their relatives is of a similar magnitude to the difference between synaesthetes and non-synaesthete controls then we do have sufficient power to detect this (at power = 0.9, $\alpha = 0.02$), but power is lost at smaller effect sizes. We also conducted multivariate analyses such that multiple smaller univariate effects between groups may yield more robust differences.

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2.1.2. Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria

All participants were aged between 18-60¹ years old, and had normal or corrected-to-normal vision, as well as sufficient English to understand the task instructions and questionnaires. To determine eligibility and group membership, prospective participants were asked to complete a brief online screening questionnaire. Here, as well as asking their gender, age and education for matching purposes, participants completed online versions of the Farnsworth Dichotomous Test (D15) and Ishihara Test for colour blindness (e.g., <https://www.color-blindness.com>). We applied public norms for determining exclusion based on colour blindness test results.

Participants were also provided with a brief description and pictorial representation of what synaesthesia is and were asked to indicate using response-boxes whether they thought that they had synaesthesia, with the options “I am sure I do not have it”, “unsure” and “I am sure I do have it” (Ward & Filiz, 2020). All relatives and controls, irrespective of their response-box selection, were subsequently provided with online consistency tests (see *Materials* for more detail about the consistency tests used for this purpose). If they passed the consistency test, they were allocated to the synaesthesia group but otherwise were included in the respective relative or control group. Those who failed to take the test were excluded. As synaesthetes recruited through our database have previously completed these tests, they were not required to repeat these online consistency tests. We note previous research demonstrating that the consistency scores of participants improves if they take repeated tests (Ovalle Fresa & Rothen, 2019). While this study did not explicitly include a synaesthete group, it is feasible to assume that these improvements at re-test may also apply to synaesthetes. Note also that we did not use individual differences in the level of consistency in any analysis nor as a proxy for synaesthetic strength (see Lacey et al., 2021), but simply as a way of confirming synaesthetic status. Although minor changes in colour associations or strength have

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¹ Deviation from pre-registered protocol: The pre-registered upper age limit was 55 years (based on Brockmole & Logie, 2013). Following difficulties recruiting sufficient numbers of relatives – particularly parents of synaesthetes, who tend to be older – the upper age limit was extended to 60 years. This change was made during the recruitment phase. All three groups (synaesthetes, relatives, controls) remained matched for age, sex, and education.

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been noted (across time), the presence of synaesthesia per se is considered an enduring trait in adulthood (Meier et al., 2014).

We excluded any session that was completed in an unrealistically fast timeframe. The pre-registered criterion of <30 minutes was appropriate for Session 1, which aligned with the anticipated duration, but was revised for Sessions 2 and 3, which were considerably shorter (medians of 37.2 and 42.3 minutes); we therefore adopted cut-offs of 18.6 and 21.1 minutes respectively.² Partial datasets where participants terminated a session early also had that session excluded. Complete sessions were included if they were relevant to one or more hypotheses (e.g., a correlation between perception and long-term memory does not require a complete short-term memory dataset).

The dependent variables consisted of accuracy (measured in degrees) for colour and location (see *Analysis plan* for more detail). As we expected mean accuracy to differ between groups, outliers were determined separately for each task, condition (colour or location) and group (synaesthetes, relatives and controls). Samples that were > 2.5 standard deviations from each group mean were excluded for the visual perception task, visual short-term memory task (removed relative to the group mean in each load condition), and the final learning block of the long-term memory task (the latter ensures participants learn to a broadly similar level but is more tolerant of differences in the learning rate).

2.1.3. Final Sample

After applying full exclusions (i.e., after participants were excluded for being too fast, having partial datasets or for otherwise not meeting inclusion criteria) we had a maximum sample of N=115 synaesthetes ($M_{Age} = 34.71$, $SD = 10.36$; 73.04% female; 64.35% university educated; of these, N=57 had grapheme-colour, N=34 had sequence-space and N=24 had both types of synaesthesia), N=80 relatives ($M_{Age} = 34.71$, $SD = 13.09$; 57.50% female; 73.75% university educated) and N=109

² Deviation from pre-registered protocol (late October 2025, prior to any formal analyses): This revision was made when data collection was nearly complete (all synaesthetes, the minimum N of 61 relatives, and approximately 90 controls had been collected). The only analyses conducted at that point were Bayesian sensitivity tests to assess whether sufficient data had been gathered to proceed; no formal analyses had been run. A median, rather than a mean, was used as the basis for the cut-offs because a small number of participants had atypically long completion times (e.g., due to not closing the browser after finishing), which would have inflated a mean-based threshold. The precise timing of this decision is verifiable from an email exchange between the first author and their PhD supervisor dated 27–28 October 2025. The robustness of the confirmatory analyses to this change is examined in the Supplementary Materials.

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controls ($M_{Age} = 36.98$, $SD = 8.54$; 66.97% female; 65.14% university educated). Groups were matched on age ($F = 1.60$, $p = 0.204$), gender distribution ($\chi^2 = 4.48$, $p = 0.107$), and on university education ($\chi^2 = 2.19$, $p = 0.335$). Within synaesthetes, those who passed the grapheme-colour consistency test only reported significantly more types of synaesthesia ($M = 3.18$, $SD = 1.72$) than those who passed the sequence-space consistency test only ($M = 2.38$, $SD = 1.48$), $t(78.00) = 2.33$, $p = .023$ (see Supplementary Tables 1 and 2).

2.2. Materials

All materials and R scripts used in the experiment are available on Open Science Framework (OSF) (see <https://osf.io/pjb6e>). The approved Stage 1 manuscript is registered at <https://osf.io/6h8dx>.

2.2.1. Consistency tests

Online versions of consistency tests were provided to relatives and controls, as well as any synaesthetes who were recruited outside of the Sussex Database (e.g., participants from synaesthesia groups on social media). We utilised a stopping rule for these tests such that, if after presenting all stimuli once, more than 90% of stimuli were not associated with a colour or spatial location, participants were advised that they “do not appear to associate stimuli with colours/spatial locations” and were given the option to click through to the main experiment or to continue for two further repetitions of the consistency test. As all synaesthetes in the Sussex database have previously completed these tests, we did not ask them to repeat them and instead ask for their recruitment ID number so that we could verify which type(s) of synaesthesia they have.

Grapheme-colour synaesthesia status was confirmed using a consistency test which included ed questions related to potential synaesthetic experiences (cf. O valle Fresa & Rothen, 2019; Rothen et al., 2013). In total we presented ed 36 stimuli (ten digits and 26 letters). Stimuli consisted ed of some of the following potential synesthetic inducers (depending on what was reported as present): the letters of the alphabet (A-Z), digits (0-9), days of the week (Monday-Sunday), months of the year (January-December). The stimuli were presented alongside a continuous colour palette (resembling a disk)

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as well as a vertical scale on the right side, which transitions from white to black. The colour palette included d a circle that respondents could adjust using the computer mouse to select colours. The vertical scale adjusted the luminance of the colours within the palette. The colour palette and luminance bar collectively represented the entire spectrum of colours that a computer screen can display. Below the colour palette, there were two buttons: one on the left labelled "OK" (used when participants are happy with the colour displayed) and the other on the right labelled "No Colour" (used when stimuli do not trigger a colour experience).

Sequence-space synaesthesia was confirmed using the method of Ward, Ipser, et al. (2018). This included both a consistency test and completion of a brief questionnaire. Similarly to the consistency test described above, participants were presented potential synaesthetic inducers (digits [0-9], days of the week [Monday-Sunday] and months of the year [January-December]) but were asked to reproduce the spatial form of the stimuli on a 2D computer screen by making mouse clicks to indicate where each item in the sequence should be placed spatially. Each stimulus was probed three times across the course of the test to test for consistency. Participants also completed the questionnaire designed to accompany the above sequence-space synaesthesia consistency test (see OSF for all questionnaires). We note that by using the questionnaire in conjunction with the sequence-space consistency test, we were better able to discriminate between synaesthetes and non-synaesthetes than through examining cut-off scores from consistency tests alone. By having converging evidence of sequence-space synaesthesia from two sources, we reduced the chances of non-synaesthetes artificially lowering their consistency score through adopting a structured order for stimuli, as has been previously reported when only consistency tests are used (van Petersen et al., 2020).

2.2.2. Visual Stimuli

Stimuli consisted of 224 distinct and identifiable everyday objects from the Bank of Standardised Stimuli (Brodeur et al., 2014). These were processed using custom R scripts (see OSF for all R scripts). First, images were converted to greyscale and modified to have a transparent

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background. Images which were too small (i.e., those that contained more than 120,000 transparent pixels) were excluded. Using the R package “anticlust” (Papenberg & Klau, 2021), the remaining images were then categorised on the basis of familiarity and visual complexity before being randomly assigned to four pseudorandom stimuli lists according to task: the practice task list consisted of four objects; the visual perception task list consisted of 45 objects; the short-term memory task list required 135 objects and were evenly split into one, three and five object memory loads and the long-term memory task list consisted of 45 objects. Each object prompted for recall had a distinct location and colour association which was not repeated over the course of the experiment. All location and colour values were generated by scripts that ensured a wide spread of colour and location values around the circle in each trial and avoided the presentation of similar colours and locations in a sequence within blocks. This was achieved by setting minimum-difference values for both colour and location, as well as jitter.

2.2.3. Questionnaires

Two questionnaires were administered as secondary measures (covariates of interest, and potential confounds):

Sussex Cognitive Styles Questionnaire (SCSQ). The SCSQ was used to investigate the visual and verbal processing preferences of participants (Mealor et al., 2016). This is a 60-item questionnaire with six subscales measuring: Imagery Ability; Technical/Spatial Cognition; Language & Word Forms; Need for Organisation; Global Bias; and Systemising Tendency. It incorporates items from a variety of previously validated questionnaires, including the Object Spatial Imagery Questionnaire (OSIQ) (Blajenkova et al., 2006) which is of particular interest in terms of dorsal versus ventral stream visual processing. Respondents rated how much they agreed or disagreed with an item using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”.

Situational Motivation Scale. We assessed potential group differences in motivation during the experiment using the self-reported Situational Motivation Scale (Guay et al., 2000). This was to measure whether individuals with synaesthesia who were recruited from participant databases were

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more motivated to engage in scientific research than control groups (Simner, 2012; Simner & Bain, 2018). The scale selected is a valid and reliable questionnaire consisting of 16-items which measure situational intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, external regulation, and amotivation. Respondents were asked an overall question of why they were currently engaged in the activity, and rated how well 16 items answered this question using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“*corresponds not at all*”) to 7 (“*corresponds exactly*”). For example, a response of “because I think this activity is interesting” may have corresponded “exactly” to why they were engaged in this activity.

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2.3. Procedure

The experiment was designed and disseminated online using the free, open-source experiment builder lab.js (Henninger et al., 2022). The tasks (visual perception, short-term memory, and long-term memory) were split across three online testing sessions, with a duration of approximately one hour per session. Prior to completing the tasks, participants were required to complete a short, separate online screening questionnaire for colour blindness and synaesthesia (the length of which varied depending on performance in the consistency tests but did not exceed 30 minutes, see Section 2.2.1. *Consistency Tests*). Session One comprised a video demonstration and practice block, the long-term memory immediate recall task, and a motivation questionnaire. Session Two took place 48-72 hours after Session One; although some participants completed Session Two outside of this window, there was no difference in the average session gap between groups ($p > 0.100$), Session Two comprised the long-term memory delayed recall task, the visual perception task, and a repeat of the motivation questionnaire. Session Three comprised the short-term memory task and Sussex Cognitive Styles Questionnaire (SCSQ), as well as a final repeat of the motivation questionnaire (see Figure 1 below for an overview of each session and Materials for further details of each task).

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Figure 1

Overview of Test Sessions

Session 1		Session 2		Session 3	
Task	Duration (mins)	Task	Duration (mins)	Task	Duration (mins)
Full instructions and video demonstration	5	Review Instructions	5	Review Instructions	5
Practice Block	3	Long-term memory (delayed)	15	Short-term memory	45
Long-term memory (immediate)	60	Visual perception	20	Sussex Cognitive Styles Questionnaire	10
Motivation questionnaire	2	Motivation questionnaire	2	Motivation questionnaire	2

Note. To identify study eligibility and group membership (synaesthetes, relative, control), prior to completing the test sessions, participants were asked to complete a short, separate screening questionnaire comprising the colour blindness and synaesthesia tests. Eligible participants had the option to complete Session One immediately following this, or to return to start the experiment later.

To ensure that stimulus size was controlled across screens, at the beginning of each test session participants were asked to sit an arm's length away from the computer screen (approximately 60cm) and a scaling task was included at the beginning of the experiment such that participants adjusted a rectangle to the size of credit card and all stimuli were scaled accordingly to be 5° × 5° of visual angle. All tasks involved d an association of object, colour, and location with object acting as the cue. Colour adjustments were made by moving the mouse around a colour wheel underlying the circle. As participants moved d the mouse around the circle, they saw a preview of the changing hue. Participants then clicked "confirm" when they were satisfied with the colour they had selected. Location adjustments were made by using the mouse to drag the grey object to the remembered location on the circle and hitting the "confirm" button. Colour and location were chosen

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sequentially on each trial, with the order of selection (colour or location first) counterbalanced between participants.

In the first session, when participants were familiarising themselves with the overall experiment and needed to learn how to submit their answers, there was a video demonstrating how to report answers using the colour and location wheels, as well as a short practice block, in addition to written instructions. This practice block consisted of viewing four different objects in different colours and locations around a circle – in essence, a short version of the long-term memory task described in detail below. These objects were presented sequentially, for two seconds each. Participants were then asked to report the remembered colour and location for each practice object in turn with feedback (see below). Subsequent sessions began with a reminder of how to submit colour and location answers, but no practice session.

Participants then completed the main task(s) for each session. The visual long-term memory task consisted of alternating learning and testing phases (three sets of 15 objects, displayed for four repetitions each) prompted for immediate recall, as well as a delayed recall only task 48-72 hours later in Session Two. Session Two contained the visual perception task which was completed in three blocks of 15 trials (45 objects). The short-term memory task was completed in Session Three with three blocks of 15 trials, split according to memory load. Block one consisted of 15 trials at memory load one (15 objects prompted), block two consisted of 15 trials at memory load three (45 objects prompted), and block three consisted of 15 trials at memory load five (75 objects prompted).

2.4.1. Long-term Memory Task

The visual long-term memory task spanned two test sessions and comprised repeated learning and test blocks (Session One) and delayed recall (Session Two). Participants were informed at the beginning of the first test session that 45 object-colour-location associations must be memorised.

In Session One, items were divided into three sets of 15 objects to learn, and the participants were

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presented with each set of objects four times. During the learning phase, each object was sequentially presented in random order for two seconds each. This was followed by a brief retention interval and the immediate recall phase during which the same objects were, sequentially presented in random order and probed for colour and location. Participants were given feedback to help them learn during the long-term memory immediate session. After each response, they were presented with a screen for two seconds that used two stacked sliding visual scales with green “✓” and red “X” label anchors at each side of the screen. The top scale displayed the participants’ accuracy for location and the bottom scale displayed the participants’ accuracy for colour. The scales were non-linear (utilising a square root function of degree of deviation) so that greater space on the scale was dedicated to deviation values between 1-45 degrees than to those between 46-180 degrees. Feedback was shown via a green dot which was placed on the scales between the two labels depending on the deviation from the correct response. At the end of each learning block, participants were also shown their total average deviations from the original colours and locations across the block using the same visual sliding scales. Block feedback was displayed in an untimed manner so that participants could review it for as long they desired before taking a break and moving on to the next learning block.

The second test session, which took place between 48-72 hours after the first session, probed for recall of the 45 object associations only, and did not involve learning and immediate recall phases. At the end of each recall block within the long-term memory delayed session (i.e., after each set of 15 objects has been probed), participants were shown their total average deviation from the original colours and locations (similar to the block feedback they saw during the “long-term memory immediate” session).

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Figure 2

Long-Term Memory Task Summary

Note. In the long-term memory immediate task, participants were asked to learn colour-location-object associations for 45 objects (split into blocks of 15 objects). These were presented sequentially for two seconds each. Participants reported the remembered location and colour as previously and were given feedback about their accuracy. In the long-term memory delayed task, which occurred 48 – 72 hours later, participants only saw grey object prompts and were requested to adjust each of the 45 items' location and colour to match its appearance from the long-term memory immediate task.

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2.4.2. Visual Perception Task

Participants were presented with two objects which were identical except for their colour and location: the one on the left acted as a target model, and the one on the right was adjusted to fit the model as accurately as possible (Figure 3). Feedback on average accuracy was provided at the end of each block of 15 objects (not at the trial level) using the same sliding scales as described above.

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Figure 3

Visual Perception Example Trial

Note. Participants were asked to adjust the colour and location of the grey object on the right side of the screen to match that on the left. Colour adjustments were made using a colour wheel underlying the circle. To make location adjustments, they used the mouse to drag the grey object to the desired position around the circle.

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2.4.2. Short-term Memory Task

To measure visual short-term memory performance, either one, three, or five different study objects in different colours at different locations were presented around a single, central circle. As mentioned, all location and colour values for the short-term memory task were generated by means of custom R scripts (see OSF) which ensured a wide spread of colour and location values around the circle in three and five load trials while preventing overlap (i.e., there was a minimum difference of 50 degrees set between location values in each array). It also avoided the presentation of similar colours and locations in a sequence across trials, including in the one object load condition, by setting minimum differences and enforcing jitter between consecutive trials. The objects in varying load conditions were presented simultaneously for a duration of two seconds. Following a delay of

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one second, participants were cued to recall the colour and location of each object from the array in turn (selected at random). Colour and location adjustments were made in the same way as the other tasks. Feedback on average accuracy was provided at the end of the block (not at the trial level).

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Figure 4

Short-Term Memory Example Trial

Note. Either one, three or five objects were presented in different colours at different positions around the circle for two seconds. Following a delay of one second, participants were asked to report the colour and location of each object from the array in turn (selected at random). Adjustments were made analogous to the other tasks.

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3. Analysis Plan

In this section, we detail our dependent variables and each of our planned analyses in turn. Please note that model-free analyses are the main source of inference for our hypotheses, and all further analyses (e.g., Bayesian, model-based, multivariate, exploratory) are to be considered secondary but are important with respect to establishing the robustness of findings and in providing supplementary information to aid interpretation (e.g., determining whether null results are sensitive).

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A table outlining our Analysis Plan and additional information, such as the results of quality assurance and pilot testing, can be found in the Supplementary Materials.

3.1. Dependent variables

Across all tasks, accuracy scores were calculated as the absolute deviation from original colour or location in degrees. Accuracy scores could fall between 0-179 degrees of deviation from the original and were separately calculated for colour and location conditions, with values closer to 0 indicating more precise recall. In the short-term memory task, accuracy scores for location and colour were calculated at three different loads (one, three and five object arrays). In the long-term memory task, accuracy scores for location and colour were calculated for three learning blocks and a final delayed recall block.

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3.2. Model-free analyses of accuracy data

3.2.1. Mixed-Factorial ANOVAs

We conducted a series of mixed-factorial Analyses of Variance (ANOVAs). The first tested the hypothesis that synaesthetes would display enhanced visual perception and memory advantages compared to other groups (i.e., will show greater accuracy across tasks) using the within-subject factor Condition (colour vs. location recall) and the between-subject factor Group (synaesthetes vs. non-synaesthetes) and, as appropriate, the within-subject factor of Array size (short-term memory) or Block number (to assess learning and forgetting rates in long-term memory) [Hypothesis 1]. To investigate whether grapheme-colour synaesthetes and sequence-space synaesthetes showed differential memory and visual perceptual abilities, we repeated the mixed-factorial ANOVAs from above but replaced binary Group (synaesthetes vs. non-synaesthetes) with a 2x2 group design based on presence/absence of grapheme-colour and presence/absence of sequence-space (where the 'double absent' group consisted of the controls) [Hypothesis 3]. To investigate the pattern of results for relatives, we entered a third Group (relatives of synaesthetes) in the mixed-factorial ANOVAs above with the within-subject factor Condition (colour vs. location recall) and the between-subject factor Group (synaesthetes vs. relatives vs. non-synaesthetes) [Hypothesis 4].

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3.2.2. Correlation Matrix (and Regression Model)

To examine the relationship between performance on perceptual tasks and corresponding memory tasks, irrespective of synaesthesia status, we conducted correlations between performance measures on the visual perception and memory tasks across all participants considering colour and location separately [Hypothesis 2a]. Given that each memory task had several levels (array size for short-term memory, block number and delay in long-term memory) the levels were averaged together in the case of a non-significant group X interaction in the ANOVA or treated separately in the case of a significant interaction.

Any significant correlations indicating an association between perceptual precision and memory precision were explored further in terms of possible confounds that might drive the association, by means of a regression model (with memory acting as dependent variable). Predictors included perceptual performance (colour or location as appropriate), group status (synaesthesia coded categorically), and other individual difference variables (cognitive styles, motivation, age) [Hypothesis 2b].

3.3. Bayesian Statistics

To establish the robustness of our findings, we also utilised Bayesian hypothesis testing to quantify the likelihood of different hypotheses given the data. Here, the evidence level was set at a Bayes factor of at least 6 times in favour of the experimental hypothesis over the null hypothesis (or *vice versa*, i.e., 1/6). Group differences (examined using ANOVAs in the frequentist approach above) were assessed using the room-to-move heuristic (Dienes, 2019, 2020) based on a prediction that synaesthetes would outperform controls and the fact that there is an a priori ceiling on their performance (0 degrees error). That is, the experimental hypothesis was modelled as a half-normal centred on the control mean with two standard deviations of the distribution defined by the room-to-move (i.e., the difference between the control mean and the ceiling of 0 degrees performance). Testing of regression slopes was based on the ratio-of-means heuristic (Dienes, 2019, 2020) such that for any pairs of tasks (e.g., colour perception vs. colour long-term memory) a rough scale of effect was determined from a line passing through the mean of the two tasks and the origin. Bayes

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Factors were interpreted according to conventional evidence categories (Jeffreys, 1998; Wagenmakers et al., 2018): for $BF \geq 6$ (evidence for an effect), 6-10 = substantial, 10-30 = strong, 30-100 = very strong, >100 = decisive; for $BF < 1/6$ (evidence for the null), 0.10-0.167 = substantial, 0.033-0.10 = strong, 0.01-0.033 = very strong, <0.01 = decisive; values between 1/6 and 6 were considered inconclusive.

3.4. Model-based analyses of Memory Precision and Guess Rate

The analyses described above take the entire distribution of responses (centred around the target response at 0 degrees) and calculates the mean. But it is also possible to calculate other derived measures based on a mixture model that assumes that the observed distribution is made up of several other component distributions: a baseline probability of guessing (modelled as a uniform distribution across all angles), a memory precision score (measured by the error distributions of participant responses) and, in some tasks, memory for a non-target (e.g., if presented a red cup, and blue chair then a cup cue may elicit a blue response which does not reflect a random guess but instead reflects feature-based memory). Precision and guessing were estimated using the R package `mixture` (Grange & Moore, 2022) for all dependent variables. Unfortunately, for the short-term memory task, we were unable to consider confusion between items due to having insufficient trials to do so reliably. See Figure 5 for an illustration of the interpretation of mixture models.

These derived dependent variables were used to help interpret significant results obtained from the primary analyses as they provided further information about the nature of individual differences in the underlying memory processes. For example, it was possible to have both high memory precision and a high guess rate if a participant learnt a small number of items well. Others may have learnt all associations but only weakly (low precision and low guessing). Enhanced memory was indicated by high precision and low guessing. (High guessing and very low precision data was likely eliminated as outliers due to a failure to engage in the task).

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Figure 5

Examples of Dependent Measure (colour) and the Two-Component Mixture Model

Note. The left image demonstrates the dependent variable in colour space. The absolute deviation of the reported colour from the original colour is measured. The right image shows a two-component mixture model fit to a histogram of response errors, including probability of guessing $p(\text{Guess})$ and the precision of retained memory representations Circular SD (σ).

3.5. Multivariate analyses

Multivariate analyses can detect group differences across multiple variables in a single analysis such that, for example, multiple small effects (with the possibility of being missed in a univariate approach) can collectively constitute a larger overall effect. We performed these analyses to quantify the cumulative impact of multiple factors (e.g., cognitive style subscales, visual perceptual accuracy), gain a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between various cognitive factors and task performance and, using related machine learning techniques, to determine whether relatives have a cognitive profile and task performance that more closely resembled a synaesthetes or an unrelated control participant.

Mahalanobis D is a multivariate effect size that is conceptually equivalent to Cohen's d (and gives values on the same scale such that small is $0.3 < d < 0.5$, medium is $0.5 < d < 0.8$, and large

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is $d > .8$). To calculate Mahalanobis D one needs to know both the univariate effect sizes but also the degree of association between them (correlations). If two variables are measuring the same entity (e.g. $r = 1$) then the univariate effect sizes are averaged (as occurs in a meta-analysis) but for other combinations the effect sizes are combined according to their degree of dissimilarity (e.g. for two univariate effect sizes of 0.3 and 0.4 where the underlying variables are fully independent, $r = 0$, then the multivariate effect size is 0.5 based on Pythagorus theorem). Here we used all the dependent variables across the tasks and questionnaires to calculate Mahalanobis D comparing the three groups (synaesthetes, relatives, non-synaesthetes) using the Del Giudice (Del Giudice, 2009) R code with unbiased estimates.

Machine learning is a particular method for transforming multivariate data into a simple univariate data (e.g., classification); for example, generating an AUC (area-under-curve) measure which can also be converted to Cohen's d . The approach is to divide the dataset into separate 'train' and 'test' partitions used to develop the algorithm (train) and then use it to predict novel data (test). In this way, machine learning is a predictive approach whereas Mahalanobis D is descriptive. We used a Random Forest classifier together with 10-fold cross-validation to classify synaesthetes and non-synaesthetes. The classifier was then used to predict the status of the relatives group which we hypothesised would be intermediate between the groups (see Ward & Filiz, 2020).

3.6. Exploratory Analysis: Impact of Number of Types of Synaesthesia

While the main hypotheses concern the differences between colour and spatial experiences, the number of types of synaesthesia that an individual has may also impact the results, (e.g., Ward, Brown, et al., 2018). For exploratory purposes, we therefore repeated the above analyses (model-free, model-based, Bayesian and multivariate) within the synaesthetes including the number of types of synaesthesia as an independent variable (instead of categorical coding for presence of grapheme-colour and sequence-space). The number of types fell between one and ten (the maximum possible in the database; see Ward & Simner [2022] for a discussion on synaesthesia grouping). We expected a dose-like effect, with individuals experiencing more types of synaesthesia to show

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the most accurate performance across all tasks and ~~to have~~ the largest multivariate effect size (Mahalanobis D), indicating a more distinct perceptual profile. Any significant effects of the number of types of synaesthesia on results ~~are~~ reported.

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4. Results

The model-free, multivariate and significant results from the planned and exploratory analyses are reported in the main text. Bayesian and Model-based analyses are presented in full in the Supplementary Materials, with brief in-text summaries. Overall, results strongly supported Hypothesis 1, with synaesthetes showing consistently higher colour and location precision than controls across visual perception (VP), short-term memory (STM), and long-term memory immediate and delayed recall tasks (LTMI and LTMD). Hypothesis 2a was supported, with perceptual precision correlating with memory performance, particularly for colour-dependent memory variables. Hypothesis 2b received partial support: perceptual precision remained a significant predictor of memory after controlling for covariates, though effects varied by task and load. Evidence for Hypothesis 3 was mixed, with grapheme-colour synaesthetes showing more consistent advantages compared to sequence-space synaesthetes as well as those with both synaesthesia types. Hypothesis 4 was not supported, with relatives not possessing a consistent intermediate cognitive style or advantage in tasks. See Table 1 for a summary of mean group performance across all tasks.

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Table 1

Summary of Group Means, Standard Deviations and Sample Sizes across all Tasks

Task	Group	Mean Colour (SD)	Mean Location (SD)	N Colour	N Location
VP	Syn (all)	3.82 (1.46)	2.63 (1.20)	102	104
	Syn (GC)	3.46 (1.17)	2.69 (1.24)	49	51
	Syn (SS)	3.88 (1.44)	2.46 (1.07)	29	30
	Syn (GC+SS)	4.31 (1.60)	2.86 (1.48)	23	24
	Controls	5.44 (2.21)	3.79 (1.62)	97	97
	Relatives	8.47 (5.24)	5.76 (4.11)	70	70
STM (Load 1)	Syn (all)	11.94 (5.04)	5.23 (2.19)	101	102
	Syn (GC)	10.81 (2.91)	5.50 (2.13)	50	51
	Syn (SS)	13.66 (5.48)	5.17 (2.17)	29	31
	Syn (GC+SS)	12.23 (3.99)	4.63 (2.32)	22	20
	Controls	15.63 (6.80)	6.27 (3.21)	104	103
	Relatives	20.07 (10.55)	6.37 (2.93)	71	71
STM (Load 3)	Syn (all)	31.79 (15.06)	18.69 (10.54)	101	101
	Syn (GC)	28.31 (13.15)	17.65 (9.97)	49	49
	Syn (SS)	36.47 (14.61)	19.00 (11.97)	30	30
	Syn (GC+SS)	33.16 (18.13)	20.62 (9.87)	22	22
	Controls	37.84 (16.60)	23.88 (12.71)	105	106
	Relatives	35.42 (15.91)	17.95 (11.22)	72	70
STM (Load 5)	Syn (all)	51.17 (20.01)	41.69 (17.88)	104	103
	Syn (GC)	47.77 (16.90)	40.27 (16.88)	51	50
	Syn (SS)	55.51 (23.04)	41.99 (19.29)	31	31
	Syn (GC+SS)	52.97 (21.61)	44.47 (18.55)	22	22
	Controls	55.72 (21.33)	44.29 (20.46)	107	107
	Relatives	45.30 (17.88)	45.30 (23.68)	74	73
LTMI	Syn (all)	28.30 (12.20)	16.40 (7.16)	112	110
	Syn (GC)	24.60 (9.08)	16.30 (7.32)	54	56
	Syn (SS)	32.60 (11.90)	16.30 (6.94)	31	32
	Syn (GC+SS)	26.20 (11.00)	18.10 (8.46)	23	24
	Controls	33.50 (13.30)	20.50 (10.20)	102	103
	Relatives	38.50 (17.00)	19.3 (12.10)	75	73
LTMD	Syn (all)	28.74 (16.80)	21.49 (13.52)	104	102
	Syn (GC)	23.29 (13.82)	18.92 (13.31)	49	49
	Syn (SS)	36.97 (18.78)	22.77 (11.97)	31	29
	Syn (GC+SS)	29.24 (15.80)	25.16 (15.11)	24	24
	Controls	34.03 (18.93)	25.04 (15.59)	96	95
	Relatives	39.05 (16.13)	24.18 (17.08)	71	71

Note: For tasks VP = visual perception; STM = short-term memory; LTMI = long-term memory immediate recall; LTMD = long-term memory delayed recall. For groups Syn (all) = all synaesthetes; Syn (GC) = grapheme-colour only; Syn (SS) = sequence-space only; Syn (GC+SS) = passed both grapheme-colour and sequence-space tests. Sample sizes differ because outlier removal was applied separately for each group, load, and condition, producing condition-specific exclusions rather than participant-level exclusions.

4.1. Hypothesis 1: Visual perception and memory advantages in synaesthetes

Synaesthetes demonstrated greater accuracy than non-synaesthetic controls across VP, STM and LTM tasks (Figure 6). In the VP task, synaesthetes were significantly more accurate than controls for both colour, $F(1, 197) = 37.57, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .16$, and location, $F(1, 199) = 33.72, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .14$. This advantage extended to STM, where a mixed ANOVA with group and load (1, 3, 5 items) revealed significant main effects of group for colour, $F(1, 209) = 8.08, p = .005, \eta^2_p = .04$, and location, $F(1, 209) = 3.99, p = .047, \eta^2_p = .02$. Load had a strong effect (colour: $F(2, 418) = 449.50, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .68$; location: $F(2, 418) = 558.21, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .73$), with accuracy decreasing as load increased, but group x load interactions were not significant, indicating that synaesthetes maintained their advantage across all memory loads. For long-term memory, synaesthetes demonstrated significantly higher accuracy than controls for immediate recall (colour: $F(1, 212) = 8.57, p = .004, \eta^2_p = .04$; location: $F(1, 211) = 11.45, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .05$) and for delayed recall of colour, $F(1, 198) = 4.38, p = .038, \eta^2_p = .02$, though the delayed recall location effect did not reach significance, $F(1, 195) = 2.93, p = .088, \eta^2_p = .01$.

Bayesian group comparisons (Supplementary Table 3) provided strong to decisive evidence for synaesthete advantages across most tasks (BFs = 7.22 – 9.30x10⁶). However, evidence was inconclusive for STM load 1 location (BF = 4.72), STM load 3 colour (BF = 4.9), LTMD colour (BF = 1.26), and LTMD location (BF = 0.67). Additionally, there was substantial evidence for the null at STM load 5 location (BF = 0.16). Model-based estimates closely paralleled the accuracy results (Supplementary Table 4). Across perception and memory tasks, synaesthetes showed higher precision (κ) than controls, with the largest group differences emerging in the perceptual task. In STM and LTM, synaesthetes also showed higher target probability (p_t) and lower guess rates (p_u), alongside the precision advantage, though these differences were modest relative to κ . In STM, synaesthetes maintained higher precision across all loads despite the expected load-related decline, and in LTM they showed clear advantages for immediate recall and smaller but still present benefits for delayed colour recall.

Figure 6

Mean Angle Absolute Deviation Across Tasks: Synaesthetes versus Controls

4.2.1. Hypothesis 2a: Relationship between perception and memory performance

Correlation analyses (collapsing across all participants) revealed that individual differences in perception predicted memory performance, with stronger relationships for colour-dependent variables (Figure 7). For STM at load 1, strong correlations were observed for both within-domain (VP colour to STM colour: $r = .57, p < .001$) and cross-domain relationships (VP location to STM colour: $r = .47, p < .001$). However, these relationships weakened at higher loads and became non-significant, or reversed in direction, at loads 3 and 5. Further analyses, reported below, show that other individual differences aside from visual perception ability exert a stronger influence at these higher loads. For LTMI, a significant within-domain correlation emerged for colour ($r = .34, p < .001$), but not for location ($r = .07, p = .239$). A significant cross-domain correlation was found for VP location predicting LTMI colour ($r = .29, p < .001$), but not for VP colour predicting LTMI location ($r = .07, p = .286$). For LTMD, significant correlations were observed for colour-dependent variables (VP colour to LTMD colour: $r = .28, p < .001$; VP location to LTMD colour: $r = .29, p < .001$) but not for location-dependent variables ($r = .05, p = .458$).

Figure 7

Matrix Heatmap of Correlations between Visual Perception and Memory

4.2.2. Hypothesis 2b: Perception–memory relationships considering synaesthesia status and covariates

Regression models examined whether perception-memory relationships remained significant when controlling for synaesthesia status, age, motivation, and cognitive style measures (Tables 2 and 3). For STM load 1, visual perception was a significant predictor in three of the four models, with particularly strong effects for within-domain colour (VP colour → STM colour: $B = 1.08, p < .001, R^2 = .43$) and cross-domain predictions of colour from location (VP location → STM colour: $B = 1.12, p < .001, R^2 = .33$). Synaesthesia status was significant in two cross-domain models ($p = .044$ and $p = .025$), but not in the within-domain analyses. At higher loads (3 and 5), visual perception was no longer a significant predictor, with age and cognitive-style factors – particularly the technical cognition subscale (associated with better performance) and global bias subscale (associated with worse performance) – emerging as the most consistent predictors across

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models. That is, participants do well at higher STM loads when they report good spatial imagery and focus more on the parts than the whole.

For long-term memory immediate recall, visual perception was a significant predictor in the within-domain colour model (VP colour → LTMI colour: $B = 1.03$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .25$) and the cross-domain predictions of colour from location (VP location → LTMI colour: $B = 1.24$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .22$), but not in the location-dependent variable models. Synaesthesia was not a significant predictor in any model. Across all analyses, older age consistently predicted poorer LTMI performance, and intrinsic motivation was a significant negative predictor in all four models (i.e., higher intrinsic motivation was associated with better performance). For delayed recall, visual perception significantly predicted colour outcomes, both within-domain (VP colour → LTMD colour: $B = 1.18$, $p < .001$) and cross-domain (VP location → LTMD colour: $B = 1.67$, $p < .001$), but did not predict location outcomes. Across all models, the LTMI–LTMD delay interval was a consistent predictor, with longer gaps associated with reduced accuracy. Older age and lower intrinsic motivation also emerged as reliable predictors of poorer delayed recall, while organisation predicted better performance in the location-based models. Synaesthesia status was not significant in any delayed long-term memory model.

Bayesian analyses supported these patterns (Supplementary Table 5). Bayesian analyses confirmed that visual perception was the only reliable predictor of memory performance. For STM load 1, VP-only models received decisive support, and adding synaesthesia or other covariates (including imagery, motivation, and cognitive-style measures) consistently reduced model evidence, indicating that these factors did not explain additional variance once perceptual precision was included. At higher STM loads (3 and 5), Bayes factors strongly favoured inconclusive or null models for all VP predictors, showing that perception-memory relationships did not persist under increased load. For long-term memory, the Bayesian results showed a clear domain-specific pattern. For LTMI, VP colour received decisive support for predicting LTMI colour ($BF = 1.27 \times 10^6$),

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and VP location received inconclusive support for predicting LTMI location ($BF = 0.18$), with covariate-augmented models generally reducing evidence relative to VP-only models. For LTMD, VP colour again showed decisive evidence for predicting LTMD colour ($BF = 3.29 \times 10^5$), whereas VP location showed consistently strong null evidence for predicting LTMD location ($BF = 0.10$). Across both LTMI and LTMD, adding synaesthesia never improved model evidence, and other covariates (age, motivation, imagery ability, and cognitive-style measures) showed weak, inconsistent, or inconclusive evidence. Together, the Bayesian results indicate that perceptual precision – not synaesthesia status or cognitive style – accounts for enhanced perception-memory relationships where they occur. The cognitive benefits linked to synaesthesia (at least in these tasks) may therefore be a consequence of their higher perceptual precision.

To bolster this conclusion, we conducted a brief exploratory (non-preregistered) mediation to test a common critique that synaesthetes' perceptual advantage could reflect greater motivation to perform well (e.g., Simner, 2019). We found that intrinsic motivation (e.g., finding the task fun) and identified regulation (e.g., thinking the task is important for them) did not mediate the synaesthesia-VP relationship (all indirect effects nonsignificant, $ps > .55$), indicating that synaesthetes' superior perception, and the downstream memory benefits it predicts, is not explained by heightened intrinsic interest or self-determined engagement. In contrast, lower external regulation and amotivation (e.g., feeling they had to do the task; not knowing if the task was worth it) produced small but reliable indirect effects ($ACME = -0.46$ to -0.62 , 95% CIs excluding zero), accounting for 14-26% of the group difference. Thus, intrinsic motivation does not appear to underlie the perception-memory pathway, although reduced pressure and disengagement contribute modestly to worse performance in controls.

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Table 2

Summary of Group Means and Standard Deviations Across all Questionnaires

Group	Intrinsic Motivation	Identified Regulation	External Regulation	Amotivation	Imagery Ability	Technical Cognition	Word Forms	Organisation	Global Bias	Systemising Tendency
Syn (all)	17.50 (5.72)	16.92 (4.96)	6.62 (3.30)	6.02 (2.87)	60.35 (6.51)	50.94 (9.83)	22.53 (3.12)	19.24 (4.60)	22.17 (2.59)	21.18 (3.71)
Syn (GC)	17.51 (5.85)	17.15 (5.15)	6.78 (3.51)	6.26 (3.11)	59.85 (6.05)	50.90 (10.18)	22.51 (3.44)	19.19 (4.61)	22.23 (2.53)	21.33 (3.55)
Syn (SS)	17.16 (5.56)	16.58 (5.01)	6.64 (3.32)	5.81 (3.04)	61.17 (7.10)	52.60 (9.05)	22.38 (2.73)	19.87 (4.30)	22.17 (2.75)	21.49 (3.94)
Syn (GC+SS)	16.74 (5.75)	16.89 (5.77)	7.17 (4.00)	6.35 (4.00)	60.68 (6.71)	54.82 (8.69)	22.09 (3.32)	20.59 (3.75)	22.36 (2.80)	22.41 (3.59)
Controls	16.34 (6.36)	16.86 (4.80)	10.12 (5.20)	8.18 (4.17)	56.68 (8.37)	47.26 (9.78)	21.61 (3.28)	19.50 (5.01)	21.81 (2.51)	19.53 (3.96)
Relatives	16.48 (4.27)	15.77 (3.71)	10.38 (4.39)	8.68 (3.95)	54.19 (8.52)	50.28 (9.03)	20.39 (3.98)	18.47 (4.26)	21.14 (3.52)	20.52 (4.12)

Note. Mean scores for each motivation subscale are shown (regressions use session-specific scores). Amotivation and external regulation are negatively scored (lower = less amotivation/externally driven). Groups did not differ on intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, organisation, or global bias.

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Table 3

Summary of Regression Analyses Predicting Memory Performance from Visual Perception Performance

Memory Outcome (Deviation)	VP Predictor (Deviation)	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>N</i>	Syn (<i>p</i>)	Other sig. predictors
Short-Term Memory (Load 1)									
STM Colour	VP Colour	1.08	0.11	9.43	<.001	.43	239	.071	—
STM Location	VP Location	0.23	0.07	3.08	.002	.13	244	.167	Technical (+), Organisation (–)
STM Location	VP Colour	0.06	0.06	1.07	.285	.11	241	.044	Technical (+), Organisation (–)
STM Colour	VP Location	1.12	0.16	6.78	<.001	.33	243	.025	—
Short-Term Memory (Load 3)									
STM Colour	VP Colour	0.48	0.33	1.49	.139	.16	241	.908	Age (–), Technical (+), Global bias (–)
STM Location	VP Location	0.20	0.35	0.59	.557	.08	243	.553	Age (–), Technical (+), Global bias (–)
STM Location	VP Colour	–0.10	0.26	–0.40	.690	.10	240	.713	Age (–), Technical (+), Global bias (–)
STM Colour	VP Location	0.72	0.44	1.64	.102	.15	244	.584	Age (–), Technical (+), Global bias (–)
Short-Term Memory (Load 5)									
STM Colour	VP Colour	0.11	0.45	0.24	.809	.16	246	.376	Age (–), Global bias (–)
STM Location	VP Location	–0.64	0.56	–1.14	.257	.17	248	.453	Age (–), Intrinsic (+), Global bias (–)
STM Location	VP Colour	–0.53	0.42	–1.28	.203	.17	245	.480	Age (–), Intrinsic (+), Technical (+), Global bias (–)
STM Colour	VP Location	0.02	0.61	0.04	.971	.16	249	.437	Age (–), Global bias (–)

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Memory Outcome (Deviation)	VP Predictor (Deviation)	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>N</i>	Syn (<i>p</i>)	Other sig. predictors
Long-Term Memory (Immediate)									
LTMI Colour	VP Colour	1.03	0.23	4.41	< .001	.25	241	.208	Age (-), Intrinsic (+)
LTMI Location	VP Location	0.30	0.23	1.27	.206	.18	242	.136	Age (-), Intrinsic (+)
LTMI Location	VP Colour	0.15	0.23	0.900	.370	.18	242	.132	Age (-), Intrinsic (+)
LTMI Colour	VP Location	1.24	0.23	3.50	< .001	.18	243	.176	Age (-), Intrinsic (+)
Long-Term Memory (Delayed)									
LTMD Colour	VP Colour	1.18	0.31	3.86	<.001	.28	241	.762	Age (-), Intrinsic (+), Gap hours (-)
LTMD Location	VP Location	0.15	0.41	0.36	.721	.18	241	.830	Age (-), Intrinsic (+), Organisation (-), Gap hours (-)
LTMD Location	VP Colour	0.08	0.30	0.27	.788	.20	241	.636	Age (-), Intrinsic (+), Organisation (-), Gap hours (-)
LTMD Colour	VP Location	1.67	0.47	3.54	<.001	.24	245	.878	Age (-), Intrinsic (+), Organisation (-), Gap hours (-)

Note: VP and memory scores are absolute angular deviations from the target; higher scores reflect worse performance. A positive *B* indicates that worse VP performance predicts worse memory performance; a negative *B* indicates the opposite. (+) = better performance; (-) = worse performance). "Gap" = LTMI-LTMD delay.

4.3. Hypothesis 3: Subtype-specific patterns of perceptual and memory precision

We conducted between-subject ANOVAs to test whether different synaesthesia subtypes showed domain-specific advantages such that grapheme-colour is linked to colour advantages, and sequence-space is linked to location advantages. Because colour and location are separate dependent variables rather than levels of a single factor, these preregistered 2x2 analyses were run separately for colour accuracy and location accuracy for each task, with grapheme-colour (yes/no) and sequence-space (yes/no) as between-subject factors. We found that grapheme-colour synaesthesia tended to be linked to stronger colour advantages than sequence space but all synaesthete groups tended to perform well on location relative to non-synaesthetes (Figure 8). To complement these preregistered analyses, we also conducted exploratory mixed ANOVAs that added condition (colour vs location) as a within-subject factor, yielding a 2x2x2 design (grapheme-colour: yes/no x sequence-space: yes/no x condition). These analyses confirmed the same pattern: across all tasks, there was a significant subtype x condition interaction driven by grapheme-colour synaesthetes, who performed better in the colour than location condition (e.g., VP: $F(1,192) = 5.56, p = .019, \eta_p^2 = .03$; STM: $F(1,196) = 10.17, p = .002, \eta_p^2 = .05$; LTMI: $F(1,202) = 19.26, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .09$). Sequence-space synaesthesia showed no corresponding location advantage (all p s $> .05$), and no additive benefits emerged for those with both subtypes.

For VP, in the planned 2x2 factorial ANOVAs, run separately for colour and location accuracy, grapheme-colour synaesthesia showed significant main effects for both colour, $F(1, 194) = 24.99, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .11$, and location, $F(1, 198) = 12.08, p = .001, \eta_p^2 = .06$, while sequence-space synaesthesia showed a significant effect only for location, $F(1, 198) = 9.46, p = .002, \eta_p^2 = .05$. Significant grapheme-colour x sequence-space interactions for both colour, $F(1, 194) = 15.87, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .08$, and location, $F(1, 198) = 10.34, p = .002, \eta_p^2 = .05$, indicated that having both types did not produce additive benefits.

For STM, using the same preregistered 2x2 design and analysing colour and location accuracy separately across loads, grapheme-colour synaesthesia showed significant main effects for

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colour, $F(1, 611) = 22.44$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .04$, and location, $F(1, 612) = 5.84$, $p = .016$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$, across all loads, while sequence-space synaesthesia showed no significant effects. For LTMI, again analysing colour and location accuracy in separate preregistered 2x2 ANOVAs, grapheme-colour synaesthesia showed significant effects for both colour, $F(1, 206) = 23.05$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .10$, and location, $F(1, 211) = 4.48$, $p = .036$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$. Sequence-space synaesthesia showed no significant main effects, $F(1, 206) = 0.004$, $p = .947$ (colour), $\eta_p^2 = < .001$, and $F(1, 211) = 1.47$, $p = .227$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$ (location). A significant grapheme-colour x sequence-space interaction for location $F(1, 211) = 4.47$, $p = .036$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$, indicated that the two synaesthesia types did not combine additively, with individuals who had only one subtype showing the strongest performance. For LTMD, in the same pre-registered 2x2 structure, grapheme-colour synaesthesia showed a significant effect for colour, $F(1, 196) = 13.77$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .07$, but not location, $F(1, 193) = 2.73$, $p = .100$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$, with no significant effects for sequence-space synaesthesia.

Bayesian group comparisons (Supplementary Table 3) confirmed this pattern: grapheme-colour synaesthetes showed very strong to decisive evidence of advantages over controls across most tasks (BFs = 36.48 – 6.3×10^7). Sequence-space synaesthetes, by contrast, showed decisive evidence only in VP (both colour and location), with inconclusive evidence in LTMI location (BF = 4.36) and LTMI colour (BF = 0.10, substantial null), and substantial to strong null evidence at higher STM loads (e.g., load 3 colour: BF = 0.12; load 5 colour: BF = 0.08). Direct comparisons between grapheme-colour and sequence-space synaesthetes yielded inconclusive evidence in VP colour (BF = 0.23) and strong null evidence in VP location (BF = 0.06), with similarly inconclusive or null results across memory tasks. Comparisons involving participants with both subtypes versus single-subtype groups consistently showed strong null evidence (BFs = 0.03 – 0.12), indicating no additive benefit. Model-based estimates also revealed clear subtype differences: grapheme-colour synaesthetes showed the highest precision and target probability across perception, STM, and LTM, while sequence-space synaesthetes showed weaker and less consistent advantages, and participants with both types typically performed at intermediate levels with no additive benefit (Supplementary Table 4). These findings reinforce the absence of a clear double dissociation.

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Figure 8

Mean Angle Absolute Deviation Across Tasks: Synaesthesia Subtypes

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Long-Term Memory – Reps 1-5 (dashed = LTM/LTMD boundary)

Long-Term Memory – LTM (Avg reps 1-4) vs LTMD

Subtype Group ■ Control ■ GC ■ SS ■ GC+SS

Note. In the bar chart visualisations, to highlight group differences, rather than the impact of task manipulation on performance, we have taken averages of STM across load and LTM across repetitions/blocks.

4.4. Hypothesis 4: Perceptual and memory performance in relatives of synaesthetes

We compared first-degree relatives with synaesthetes and controls to examine whether relatives display intermediate performance suggestive of an endophenotype (Figure 9). Contrary to this hypothesis, relatives did not show intermediate performance but instead demonstrated high variability and, in many cases, significantly worse performance than both other groups. For VP, relatives performed significantly less accurately than both synaesthetes and controls for both colour, $F(2, 266) = 46.66, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .26$ and location, $F(2, 268) = 35.14, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .21$ (all pairwise $ps < .001$), with substantially larger standard deviations than either comparison group.

For STM, we conducted separate mixed ANOVAs for colour and location, each with group (synaesthetes, relatives, controls) as a between-subject factor and load (1,3,5) as a within-subjects factor. These revealed significant main effects of group (colour: $F(2, 277) = 3.70, p = .026, \eta^2_p = .03$; location: $F(2, 277) = 3.84, p = .023, \eta^2_p = .03$) and significant group x load interactions (colour: $F(4, 554) = 8.96, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .06$; location: $F(4, 554) = 6.65, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .05$). Post-hoc comparisons indicated that relatives were less accurate than synaesthetes at load 1, while at load 5 they showed a different pattern (more accurate than controls for colour but less accurate than both groups for location), accompanied by extremely high variability. For LTMI, relatives performed significantly less accurately than both synaesthetes and controls for colour, $F(2, 286) = 14.38, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .09$. For location, synaesthetes performed more accurately than controls, $F(2, 283) = 6.34, p = .002, \eta^2_p = .04$, with no significant difference between relatives and controls or between synaesthetes and relatives. For LTMD, relatives performed significantly less accurately than synaesthetes for colour, $F(2, 268) = 7.51, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .05$, but not significantly different from controls, while for location no group effect was observed, $F(2, 265) = 1.44, p = .239, \eta^2_p = .01$.

Critically, when comparing relatives to controls, there was very strong evidence for the null hypothesis across VP (colour: $BF = 0.02$; location: $BF = 0.03$), STM load 1 (colour: $BF = 0.02$; location: $BF = 0.06$, strong null), and LTMI (colour: $BF = 0.02$, very strong null; location: $BF = 0.15$,

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substantial null), indicating that despite significant p-values in the model-free tests, relatives did not differ meaningfully from controls in these tasks. For LTMD, there was similarly very strong null evidence for colour (BF = 0.03) and substantial null evidence for location (BF = 0.14). However, at higher STM loads (load 3 and 5), the pattern diverged: relatives showed very strong null evidence compared to synaesthetes (e.g., load 5: colour BF = 0.03, location BF = 0.03), but strong evidence that relatives outperformed controls at load 5 (colour: BF = 11.07; location: BF = 68.13). Model-based parameters reinforced that relatives did not show intermediate performance between synaesthetes and controls. Instead, they showed lower precision and target probability, and higher guess rates, across perception, STM, and LTM. Together, these findings indicate that relatives do not exhibit the predicted intermediate or graded pattern of performance (Supplementary Table 4).

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Figure 9

Mean Angle Absolute Deviation Across Tasks: Synaesthetes, Relatives and Controls

4.5. Multivariate analyses

4.5.1. Machine Learning Classification

The random forest model was trained to distinguish synaesthetes from controls using 14 non-synaesthesia-specific measures (6 cognitive style questionnaire variables and 8 task accuracy variables) and achieved 70.2% accuracy in 10-fold cross validation ($\kappa = .41$). When applied to relatives, 26.7% (16 of the 60 for whom we have complete cases) were classified as resembling the synaesthete cognitive profile, with a mean probability of synaesthete classification of .41.

4.5.2. Multivariate Effect Sizes

Mahalanobis D analyses were conducted using the same 14 non-synaesthesia-specific measures. Large multivariate differences were observed across all comparisons (Table 4; for univariate results see Supplementary Table 6). Synaesthetes and controls showed substantial separation ($D_u = 0.97$, 95% CI [0.63, 1.12]; OVL = .63; PCC = .69). Relatives showed even greater distance from controls ($D_u = 1.08$, 95% CI [0.50, 1.27]; OVL = .59; PCC = .71), equivalent to 112% of the synaesthete-control distance. The largest separation was between synaesthetes and relatives ($D_u = 1.44$, 95% CI [0.99, 1.63]; OVL = .47; PCC = .77), at 149% of the synaesthete-control distance. Tucker's coefficients indicated moderately similar correlation structures for synaesthetes versus controls (CC = .88), but greater heterogeneity for relatives versus controls (CC = .71) and synaesthetes versus relatives (CC = .75).

Table 4

Multivariate Effect Sizes Between Groups

Comparison	D_u	95% CI	OVL	PCC	CC
Synaesthetes vs Controls	0.97	[0.63, 1.12]	.63	.69	.88
Relatives vs Controls	1.08	[0.50, 1.27]	.59	.71	.71
Synaesthetes vs Relatives	1.44	[0.99, 1.63]	.47	.77	.75

Note. D_u = bias-corrected Mahalanobis D; OVL = overlap coefficient; PCC = probability of correct classification; CC = Tucker's coefficient of congruence.

4.6. Impact of Number of Types of Synaesthesia

Previous analyses distinguished the presence or absence of synaesthesia and subtype group (grapheme-colour only, sequence-space only, or both, based on consistency tests). Here, we extend this approach by examining the number of synaesthesia types reported per individual across a broad range of types (e.g., lexical–gustatory), with individuals reporting up to nine types in practice (see Supplementary Tables 1 and 2 for prevalence). Across all tasks, model-free analyses showed that the number of synaesthesia types was not significantly associated with performance. This was confirmed in Bayesian analyses which consistently favoured the null, as well as in model-based comparisons of the precision of synaesthetes with “few types” (\leq median = 3) and “many types” ($>$ median) (Supplementary Tables 7-9).

We also adapted the multivariate approach to test whether synaesthetes with more types showed more distinctive cognitive profiles. Number of types was analysed both continuously (correlations and linear regressions) and categorically via a median split. In continuous analyses, number of types significantly predicted imagery ability ($\beta = 1.24$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .13$) and systemising ($\beta = 0.55$, $p = .003$, $R^2 = .08$), with no associations for the remaining 12 variables (all $ps > .10$). Multivariate group comparison showed a moderate overall difference of many versus few types (bias-corrected Mahalanobis $D_u = 0.63$, 95% CI [0.00, 0.76]; OVL = .75; PCC = .62), with moderately similar correlation structures across groups (CC = .69). Univariate effects indicated that this multivariate difference was driven mainly by imagery ability ($d = 0.71$, higher in many-types), with smaller effects for systemising ($d = 0.36$, higher in many-types) and visual perception (colour: $d = -0.31$, location: $d = -0.31$, indicating slightly worse perceptual performance in many-types synaesthetes). All other effects were negligible. Overall, synaesthetes with more types showed a moderately distinct multivariate cognitive profile, primarily reflected in higher self-reported imagery and systemising rather than differences in objective task performance.

4.7. Robustness checks

To assess the sensitivity of the confirmatory results to the revised session-duration exclusion criterion (see footnote 2, Section 2.1.2), three additional analyses were conducted using alternative

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cut-offs: a lenient criterion (half the 25th-percentile completion time), a strict criterion (half the 75th-percentile), and the original pre-registered fixed threshold of 30 minutes. Full results are presented in Supplementary Tables 13-16. For the STM task, the pattern of significant and non-significant effects was identical across all four criteria. For VP and LTMI, results were likewise highly consistent across criteria. The one effect worth noting is LTMD Hypothesis 1 colour, which is significant in the main analysis ($p = .038$) but marginal under the strict criterion ($p = .096$) and non-significant under the original 30-minute threshold ($p = .236$); however, effect size is relatively stable across all four criteria ($\eta^2p \approx .010-.022$), suggesting these fluctuations reflect reduced power from the greater data loss under more aggressive exclusion rather than an unstable effect. One Hypothesis 3 effect, the GCS x SSS interaction for location in the VP task, is significant under the main and lenient criteria but not under the strict or original threshold ($\eta^2p \approx .010-.045$), again consistent with a power-driven fluctuation. Taken together, the robustness checks support the conclusions drawn from the main confirmatory analysis.

5. Discussion

This study fills a key gap by examining perception and memory within a unified framework, using closely matched tasks that produce the same dependent measure. Together with a large and varied synaesthete sample and the most comprehensive assessment to date of first-degree relatives' cognitive style and perceptual-memory abilities, this approach provides a strong foundation for understanding how synaesthesia relates to broader perceptual and memory processes. In the context of this design, we found that synaesthetes demonstrated clear advantages in visual perception and memory, most robustly for perceptual colour precision and for memory under low load and immediate long-term recall; these advantages were weaker or absent at higher STM loads. Individual differences in perceptual precision predicted memory performance, particularly at lower memory loads, and once perceptual precision (particularly VP colour) was included, adding synaesthesia status did not improve model evidence: Bayes factors consistently decreased when synaesthesia was added, indicating that memory advantages are largely mediated by perceptual precision rather than synaesthesia *per se*. Grapheme-colour synaesthesia drove most of these benefits, showing

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consistent advantages across perception, STM, and LTM tasks for both colour and location, whereas sequence-space synaesthesia produced significant effects only in visual perception (location condition), with largely null or inconclusive effects in memory tasks. Contrary to an endophenotype hypothesis, first-degree relatives of synaesthetes did not display intermediate performance on the tasks nor a cognitive profile more similar to their synaesthetic family members.

These findings provide support for the enhanced processing account of cognitive differences in synaesthesia. According to the dual-coding account, synaesthetes' memory advantages should be limited to situations where their synaesthetic experiences provide additional retrieval cues (Ghirardelli et al., 2010; Smilek et al., 2005). However, synaesthetes with varying subtypes outperformed non-synaesthetes on both colour and location memory tasks, and once perceptual precision was accounted for, synaesthesia status itself ceased to be a significant predictor in most models. This pattern suggests that cognitive advantages arise from more fundamental differences in perceptual and memory systems rather than from the strategic use of synaesthetic experiences (Ovalle-Fresa et al., 2021). The results align with a representational account in which the same neural substrates support processing of particular kinds of information across perception, short-term memory, and long-term memory (Graham et al., 2010; Cowell et al., 2010, 2019). Our finding that individual differences in perceptual precision strongly predicted memory performance – particularly for the same visual characteristics – is consistent with this account.

The weakening of perception-memory relationships at higher loads of the short-term memory task (loads 3 and 5), where age and cognitive style emerged as predictors, suggests limits to the extent that perceptual precision alone determines memory outcomes. When task demands exceed capacity limits, strategic processes and executive functions may become more critical than the quality of underlying perceptual representations (e.g., Cowan, 2001; Luck & Vogel, 1997; Oberauer, 2002). It is worth noting that at higher loads, the types of errors participants make may also shift from imprecision in feature representation to other error types such as swap errors (reporting the feature of a non-target item). Our study design did not include sufficient trials to

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model such errors separately, but if synaesthetes were making precise responses to the wrong items whilst controls were making imprecise guesses, this could contribute to the reduced predictive power of perceptual precision at higher loads.

We hypothesised that different forms of synaesthesia would be associated with domain-specific cognitive advantages, reflecting enhanced processing in distinct visual pathways. Specifically, we predicted enhanced colour functioning in grapheme-colour synaesthetes and enhanced location functioning in sequence-space synaesthetes, which we assumed to reflect differential sensitivity of ventral and dorsal visual pathways in these groups. Contrary to these predictions, grapheme-colour synaesthesia was associated with advantages across almost all tasks, spanning both colour and spatial domains, whereas sequence-space synaesthesia, while showing a tendency toward some *relative* domain-specific advantages (i.e., their advantage over controls was more pronounced for location than colour trials), had less conclusive evidence of enhanced memory overall. The broad advantages shown by grapheme-colour synaesthetes are consistent with enhanced ventral stream functioning extending beyond simple colour processing. The ventral stream processes shape, texture, and complex visual patterns, and plays a critical role in visual memory (Graham et al., 2010). Although previous research found that grapheme-colour synaesthetes do not reliably show enhanced memory for object locations alone (Rothen & Meier, 2010; Yaro & Ward, 2018; Pritchard et al., 2013), our results suggest that when location is bound to a salient visual feature like colour, they may benefit from their enhanced feature processing.

The pattern of results across synaesthesia subtypes warrants close attention. One possibility is that the spatial representations involved in sequence-space synaesthesia differ fundamentally from the representations of object locations in external space required by our tasks. Sequence-space synaesthetes experience ordinal sequences (numbers, months, days of the week) as occupying specific locations in peripersonal or extrapersonal space, often described as visual forms or "number lines" (Eagleman, 2009; Brang et al., 2010). These spatial representations may be highly specialised for ordinality and sequence processing rather than for encoding arbitrary

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visuospatial configurations. Indeed, previous research has shown that sequence-space synaesthetes demonstrate enhanced performance on tasks involving ordinal information and sequential memory (van Petersen et al., 2020), but these advantages may not extend to tasks requiring memory for the spatial locations of discrete objects. Our task required participants to remember where specific coloured objects appeared on the screen – a fundamentally different spatial challenge from navigating an internal mental timeline. Another possibility is that the dorsal stream's role lies primarily in spatial attention rather than in directly enhancing the acuity of spatial representations (Perry & Fallah, 2014). While ventral stream function has been central to accounts proposing improved representational fidelity, there is currently no clear commensurate evidence that dorsal stream mechanisms themselves increase precision, although attentional modulation could indirectly influence decision-making and the quality of encoded representations (Hebart & Hesselmann, 2012; Moraresku et al., 2024; Perry & Fallah, 2014). Future research employing tasks designed to investigate the sequential, ordinal nature of sequence-space synaesthetes' experiences, as well as disentangle spatial attention from spatial memory, might reveal more robust spatial advantages in this population.

An unexpected finding concerns the role of visual imagery. Despite synaesthetes reporting higher self-rated imagery ability than non-synaesthetes (as noted many times before, e.g. Barnett & Newell, 2008), imagery vividness did not contribute to any of our memory models. Like visual perception, imagery has been proposed to fractionate into ventral routes (linked to vividness of imagined objects) and dorsal routes (linked to spatial manipulations, such as mental rotation) (Blazhenkova, 2016; D'Angiulli et al., 2024; Koshino et al., 2005). We found that the latter was predictive of short-term memory (the technical subscale), whereas the former was a sensitive null. The fact that perceptual precision, but not imagery vividness, influenced memory performance further supports enhanced processing and representational accounts over the dual-coding account, as the fidelity of underlying neural representations is advantageous, rather than phenomenological experience or additional imagery-based encoding strategies.

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A further unforeseen finding was that first-degree relatives of synaesthetes did not display the intermediate cognitive profile expected under a simple endophenotype model. Rather than performing between synaesthetes and controls, relatives showed high variability and often performed significantly worse than both groups, particularly in visual perception tasks. It is possible that it was this difference in perceptual acuity that drove the seeming dissimilarity between synaesthetes and their relatives in our tasks, suggesting that certain cognitive style traits may be more heritable than the perceptual and working memory abilities we measured (Ward & Filiz, 2020). Multivariate and machine learning analyses further indicated that relatives were, on average, cognitively more distant from synaesthetes than unrelated controls, yet they remained distinguishable from controls, with only a minority (26.7%) classified as resembling the synaesthete cognitive profile. While these results do not support a straightforward genetic endophenotype account, the high variability suggests this group may be heterogeneous, with genetic predispositions towards synaesthesia having complex, non-linear effects that do not manifest as attenuated synaesthete-like traits. Whether the cognitive profiles of relatives vary as a function of the specific type of synaesthesia present in their family, or whether families with multiple synaesthesia types show different patterns, remain open questions.

A limitation to note is that our participant groups were recruited through different channels, with synaesthetes primarily recruited through our existing database, controls via Prolific, and relatives online and through synaesthetes themselves. Whilst this raises the possibility of systematic differences in motivation (particularly in external regulation and amotivation which may closely track recruitment) or familiarity with research procedures, the clear and consistent differences observed within synaesthetes, as well as between synaesthetes and controls across multiple tasks, suggest that our findings reflect genuine group differences rather than artefacts of recruitment. Moreover, groups did not differ in levels of intrinsic motivation and its inclusion as a covariate in regression analyses did not substantially alter the pattern of results. The unexpectedly high variability in relatives, whilst theoretically informative, also meant that our power to detect subtle pat-

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terns or subgroup differences within this group was limited. We also note that a subset ($n=7$) of relatives were reclassified as synaesthetes after completing the consistency tests. Given that consistency thresholds impose a categorical boundary on what is likely a graded trait, this raises the possibility that the relatives who remained in the comparison group represent the lower end of synaesthesia-like tendencies. If so, our analyses may reflect a somewhat restricted portion of the broader relative population.

A further distinction that we have not assessed in the present data is the difference between projector and associator forms of synaesthesia – those who experience their concurrents externally in space versus internally in the “mind’s eye.” Projector synaesthetes typically report more vivid and spatially externalised experiences and are sometimes described as having a “stronger” form of synaesthesia, which may lead to different patterns of perceptual or memory advantages compared to associators (Amsel et al., 2017; Dixon et al., 2004). There are also suggestions that projector-type experiences rely more heavily on bottom-up processes (Lungu et al., 2021). Examining whether projector–associator differences map onto distinct profiles of enhanced processing could therefore help clarify whether the phenomenology of synaesthetic experience plays a mechanistic role in these advantages, or whether it simply reflects underlying representational differences.

5.1. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that synaesthetes possess robust advantages in visual perception and memory for colour and location, driven primarily by enhanced perceptual precision rather than strategic use of synaesthetic experiences, effort, or conscious imagery. Grapheme-colour synaesthesia conferred broad cognitive benefits extending to both colour and spatial domains, suggesting that colour may play a central role in structuring visual representations. Individual differences in perceptual performance, irrespective of group, strongly predicted memory outcomes, supporting a representational account in which shared neural substrates underpin the processing of specific visual information across tasks, although these relationships were somewhat attenuated under

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high-load short-term memory conditions. First-degree relatives did not show intermediate performance, although some cognitive style measures did exhibit intermediate patterns, challenging simple endophenotype models. These findings advance understanding of the perception-memory relationship, the nature of cognitive differences in synaesthesia, and highlight the challenges of identifying endophenotypes for complex cognitive traits, underscoring the value of studying individual differences in healthy special populations as a window into fundamental principles of cognitive processing and representation.

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Supplementary Materials

Table 1

Prevalence of Number of Synaesthesia Types by Subtype Group

Group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Total
GC only	8 (14.0%)	18 (31.6%)	8 (14.0%)	11 (19.3%)	7 (12.3%)	3 (5.3%)	1 (1.8%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.8%)	57
SS only	14 (41.2%)	6 (17.6%)	5 (14.7%)	6 (17.6%)	2 (5.9%)	1 (2.9%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	34
Both	0 (0.0%)	9 (37.5%)	5 (20.8%)	1 (4.2%)	2 (8.3%)	2 (8.3%)	3 (12.5%)	1 (4.2%)	1 (4.2%)	24

Note. Numbers represent count (percentage within each subtype group). GC only means the individual passed only the grapheme-colour consistency test. SS only means the individual passed only the sequence-space consistency test.

Table 2

Prevalence of Each Synaesthesia Type by Subtype Group

Synaesthesia Type	GC only	SS only	Both
Grapheme-colour	57 (100.0%)	10 (29.4%)	24 (100.0%)
Sensation-colour	18 (31.6%)	7 (20.6%)	8 (33.3%)
Sensation-shape	22 (38.6%)	7 (20.6%)	9 (37.5%)
Lexical-gustatory	5 (8.8%)	2 (5.9%)	1 (4.2%)
Sequence-space	28 (49.1%)	34 (100.0%)	24 (100.0%)
Personification	20 (35.1%)	5 (14.7%)	8 (33.3%)
Mirror-touch	10 (17.5%)	2 (5.9%)	8 (33.3%)
Ticker-tape	12 (21.1%)	8 (23.5%)	7 (29.2%)
Auditory-visual	9 (15.8%)	6 (17.6%)	8 (33.3%)

Note. Numbers represent count (percentage within each subtype group). All nine synaesthesia types are shown, ordered by overall prevalence.

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Table 3

Summary of Bayesian Group Comparisons (ANOVA equivalent), by Task and Group Comparison

Group Comparison	Condition	Load	M1	M2	t(df)	p	BF	Interpretation
VP								
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	—	3.82	5.44	-6.07 (164.98)	<.001	9.30e+06	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	2.63	3.79	-5.75 (176.96)	<.001	1.53e+06	Decisive (effect)
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	—	3.56	5.44	-6.36 (140.39)	<.001	6.30e+07	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	2.69	3.79	-4.59 (126.41)	<.001	4596.46	Decisive (effect)
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	—	3.88	5.44	-4.45 (71.00)	<.001	2474.15	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	2.46	3.79	-5.22 (73.23)	<.001	104266.99	Decisive (effect)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	—	4.31	5.44	-2.81 (44.18)	0.007	7.43	Substantial (effect)
	Location	—	2.71	3.79	-3.40 (39.60)	0.002	51.36	Very strong (effect)
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	3.56	3.88	-0.99 (55.90)	0.327	0.23	Inconclusive
	Location	—	2.69	2.46	0.89 (68.26)	0.374	0.06	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	—	4.31	3.56	1.94 (37.12)	0.06	0.04	Strong (null)
	Location	—	2.71	2.69	0.05 (40.57)	0.958	0.12	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	4.31	3.88	0.99 (44.75)	0.329	0.06	Strong (null)
	Location	—	2.71	2.46	0.75 (42.00)	0.458	0.08	Strong (null)
Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	—	3.82	8.47	-7.24 (76.38)	<.001	3.24e+10	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	2.63	5.76	-6.20 (77.05)	<.001	3.30e+07	Decisive (effect)
Rel vs Con	Colour	—	8.47	5.44	4.56 (86.85)	<.001	0.02	Very strong (null)
	Location	—	5.76	3.79	3.80 (84.53)	<.001	0.03	Very strong (null)
STM								
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	1	11.94	15.63	-4.70 (171.76)	<.001	6207.88	Decisive (effect)
	Location	1	5.23	6.27	-2.71 (179.88)	0.007	4.72	Inconclusive
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	1	10.81	15.63	-6.15 (150.49)	<.001	1.60e+07	Decisive (effect)
	Location	1	5.5	6.27	-1.76 (139.26)	0.08	0.62	Inconclusive
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	1	13.66	15.63	-1.62 (54.49)	0.111	0.54	Inconclusive
	Location	1	5.17	6.27	-2.19 (73.22)	0.032	1.70	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	1	12.23	15.63	-3.15 (50.75)	0.003	19.04	Strong (effect)
	Location	1	4.63	6.27	-2.70 (34.94)	0.011	7.13	Substantial (effect)
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	1	10.81	13.66	-2.60 (37.32)	0.013	4.53	Inconclusive
	Location	1	5.5	5.17	0.68 (62.61)	0.501	0.06	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	1	12.23	10.81	1.50 (31.20)	0.144	0.03	Strong (null)
	Location	1	4.63	5.5	-1.46 (32.39)	0.154	0.57	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	1	12.23	13.66	-1.08 (48.95)	0.286	0.30	Inconclusive
	Location	1	4.63	5.17	-0.83 (38.76)	0.41	0.28	Inconclusive

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Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	1	11.94	20.07	-6.17 (85.50)	<.001	2.21e+07	Decisive (effect)
	Location	1	5.23	6.37	-2.79 (121.91)	0.006	6.20	Substantial (effect)
Rel vs Con	Colour	1	20.07	15.63	3.13 (109.33)	0.002	0.02	Very strong (null)
	Location	1	6.37	6.27	0.22 (159.03)	0.824	0.06	Strong (null)
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	3	31.79	37.84	-2.74 (203.31)	0.007	4.90	Inconclusive
	Location	3	18.69	23.88	-3.20 (201.19)	0.002	22.38	Strong (effect)
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	3	28.31	37.84	-3.84 (116.25)	<.001	203.36	Decisive (effect)
	Location	3	17.65	23.88	-3.31 (117.10)	0.001	36.48	Very strong (effect)
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	3	36.47	37.84	-0.44 (52.36)	0.664	0.12	Substantial (null)
	Location	3	19	23.88	-1.95 (49.08)	0.057	1.32	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	3	33.16	37.84	-1.12 (28.85)	0.273	0.35	Inconclusive
	Location	3	20.62	23.88	-1.34 (37.07)	0.188	0.45	Inconclusive
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	3	28.31	36.47	-2.50 (56.51)	0.015	3.97	Inconclusive
	Location	3	17.65	19	-0.52 (53.05)	0.606	0.22	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	3	33.16	28.31	1.13 (31.33)	0.268	0.07	Strong (null)
	Location	3	20.62	17.65	1.17 (40.87)	0.249	0.07	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	3	33.16	36.47	-0.71 (39.31)	0.484	0.25	Inconclusive
	Location	3	20.62	19	0.53 (49.25)	0.597	0.11	Substantial (null)
Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	3	31.79	35.42	-1.51 (147.82)	0.133	0.39	Inconclusive
	Location	3	18.69	17.95	0.44 (142.43)	0.663	0.07	Strong (null)
Rel vs Con	Colour	3	35.42	37.84	-0.98 (156.86)	0.331	0.17	Inconclusive
	Location	3	17.95	23.88	-3.25 (160.00)	0.001	29.42	Strong (effect)
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	5	51.17	55.72	-1.60 (208.75)	0.112	0.34	Inconclusive
	Location	5	41.69	44.29	-0.98 (206.11)	0.328	0.16	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	5	47.77	55.72	-2.54 (121.66)	0.013	2.76	Inconclusive
	Location	5	40.27	44.29	-1.29 (114.45)	0.198	0.29	Inconclusive
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	5	55.51	55.72	-0.05 (45.94)	0.963	0.08	Strong (null)
	Location	5	41.99	44.29	-0.57 (51.21)	0.568	0.15	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	5	52.97	55.72	-0.55 (30.01)	0.589	0.15	Substantial (null)
	Location	5	44.47	44.29	0.04 (32.41)	0.967	0.10	Strong (null)
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	5	47.77	55.51	-1.62 (49.64)	0.111	0.6	Inconclusive
	Location	5	40.27	41.99	-0.41 (57.34)	0.684	0.14	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	5	52.97	47.77	1.00 (32.58)	0.323	0.06	Strong (null)
	Location	5	44.47	40.27	0.91 (36.98)	0.37	0.06	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	5	52.97	55.51	-0.41 (47.09)	0.683	0.16	Substantial (null)
	Location	5	44.47	41.99	0.47 (46.44)	0.64	0.09	Strong (null)
Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	5	51.17	45.34	1.72 (139.58)	0.088	0.03	Very strong (null)
	Location	5	41.69	32.92	2.82 (135.08)	0.005	0.03	Very strong (null)

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Rel vs Con	Colour	5	45.34	55.72	-3.00 (145.37)	0.003	11.07	Strong (effect)
	Location	5	32.92	44.29	-3.52 (147.92)	<.001	68.13	Very strong (effect)
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LTMI								
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	—	28.35	33.45	-2.92 (205.30)	0.004	7.22	Substantial (effect)
	Location	—	16.39	20.47	-3.34 (181.23)	0.001	31.38	Very strong (effect)
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	—	26.15	33.45	-3.71 (134.65)	<.001	110.59	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	15.65	20.47	-3.55 (147.85)	<.001	71.28	Very strong (effect)
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	—	32.6	33.45	-0.34 (54.94)	0.735	0.10	Substantial (null)
	Location	—	16.35	20.47	-2.59 (76.44)	0.011	4.36	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	—	28.07	33.45	-1.69 (33.20)	0.1	0.75	Inconclusive
	Location	—	18.13	20.47	-1.17 (40.35)	0.248	0.34	Inconclusive
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	26.15	32.6	-2.49 (58.01)	0.016	3.46	Inconclusive
	Location	—	15.65	16.35	-0.46 (63.02)	0.648	0.14	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	—	28.07	26.15	0.59 (35.30)	0.558	0.08	Strong (null)
	Location	—	18.13	15.65	1.27 (36.22)	0.212	0.05	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	28.07	32.6	-1.26 (44.64)	0.214	0.43	Inconclusive
	Location	—	18.13	16.35	0.84 (43.83)	0.406	0.08	Strong (null)
Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	—	28.35	38.53	-5.37 (151.70)	<.001	177457.98	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	16.39	19.32	-2.54 (143.27)	0.012	2.94	Inconclusive
Rel vs Con	Colour	—	38.53	33.45	2.54 (161.60)	0.012	0.02	Very strong (null)
	Location	—	19.32	20.47	-0.84 (172.58)	0.403	0.15	Substantial (null)
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LTMD								
Syn (all) vs Con	Colour	—	28.74	34.03	-2.08 (190.47)	0.039	1.26	Inconclusive
	Location	—	21.49	25.04	-1.70 (186.63)	0.09	0.67	Inconclusive
Syn (GC) vs Con	Colour	—	23.29	34.03	-3.89 (125.69)	<.001	292.59	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	18.92	25.04	-2.46 (111.42)	0.015	3.93	Inconclusive
Syn (SS) vs Con	Colour	—	36.97	34.03	0.76 (51.17)	0.453	0.07	Strong (null)
	Location	—	22.77	25.04	-0.83 (59.71)	0.411	0.24	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Con	Colour	—	29.24	34.03	-1.27 (41.18)	0.21	0.44	Inconclusive
	Location	—	25.16	25.04	0.04 (36.38)	0.972	0.14	Substantial (null)
Syn (GC) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	23.29	36.97	-3.50 (50.39)	<.001	89.62	Very strong (effect)
	Location	—	18.92	22.77	-1.32 (63.99)	0.193	0.54	Inconclusive
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (GC)	Colour	—	29.24	23.29	1.57 (40.73)	0.124	0.07	Strong (null)
	Location	—	25.16	18.92	1.72 (40.98)	0.093	0.07	Strong (null)
Syn (GC+SS) vs Syn (SS)	Colour	—	29.24	36.97	-1.66 (52.59)	0.104	0.92	Inconclusive
	Location	—	25.16	22.77	0.63 (43.47)	0.533	0.11	Substantial (null)
Syn (all) vs Rel	Colour	—	28.74	39.05	-4.08 (154.48)	<.001	517.58	Decisive (effect)
	Location	—	21.49	24.18	-1.11 (127.56)	0.269	0.32	Inconclusive

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Rel vs Con	Colour	—	39.05	34.03	1.85 (161.66)	0.067	0.03	Very strong (null)
	Location	—	24.18	25.04	-0.33 (142.99)	0.74	0.14	Substantial (null)

Note: Bayes Factor (BF) interpretations based on 1/6 and 6 sensitivity thresholds. For $BF \geq 6$ (evidence for effect): 6-10 = Substantial, 10-30 = Strong, 30-100 = Very Strong, >100 = Decisive. For $BF < 1/6$ (evidence for null hypothesis): 0.10-0.167 = Substantial, 0.033-0.10 = Strong, 0.01-0.033 = Very Strong, <0.01 = Decisive. Values between 1/6 (0.167) and 6 are considered Inconclusive. Lower M values indicate better performance (higher accuracy)

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Table 4
Summary of Model-based Analyses, by Task and Group

Task	Group	Condition	Load	Dependent Variable	M(SD)	t(df) vs 0	p
VP	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	209.17 (139.03)	15.12 (100)	<.001
VP	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	228.31 (130.18)	12.02 (46)	<.001
VP	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	207.50 (162.08)	7.13 (30)	<.001
VP	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	172.33 (120.00)	6.89 (22)	<.001
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Con	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	112.73 (84.33)	13.10 (95)	<.001
VP	Con	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Con	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.02)	—	—
VP	Rel	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	90.00 (100.06)	7.58 (70)	<.001
VP	Rel	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.04)	—	—
VP	Rel	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.04)	—	—
VP	Syn (all)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	372.69 (235.76)	16.28 (105)	<.001
VP	Syn (all)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (all)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	371.34 (237.91)	11.15 (50)	<.001
VP	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	384.48 (224.45)	9.54 (30)	<.001
VP	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	360.35 (254.24)	6.94 (23)	<.001
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Con	Location	—	Precision (κ)	210.98 (159.14)	12.99 (95)	<.001
VP	Con	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Con	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
VP	Rel	Location	—	Precision (κ)	206.73 (228.26)	7.68 (71)	<.001
VP	Rel	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.04)	—	—
VP	Rel	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.04)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	24.24 (15.18)	16.05 (100)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.96 (0.07)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.04 (0.07)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	25.07 (14.83)	11.95 (49)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.04)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.04)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	21.00 (13.21)	8.70 (29)	<.001

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STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.94 (0.09)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.06 (0.09)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	26.91 (18.32)	6.73 (20)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.96 (0.07)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.04 (0.07)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	16.70 (11.80)	14.43 (103)	<.001
STM	Con	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.96 (0.08)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.04 (0.08)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	1	Precision (κ)	11.87 (9.64)	10.44 (71)	<.001
STM	Rel	Colour	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.94 (0.16)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.06 (0.16)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	109.68 (92.53)	11.79 (98)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	93.45 (67.91)	9.63 (48)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	118.00 (94.23)	6.86 (29)	<.001
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.01)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	136.96 (131.84)	4.65 (19)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	1.00 (0.02)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.00 (0.02)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	90.54 (61.96)	14.83 (102)	<.001
STM	Con	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.05)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.05)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	3	Precision (κ)	84.75 (62.69)	11.39 (70)	<.001
STM	Rel	Colour	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.98 (0.06)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.02 (0.06)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	16.28 (21.05)	7.85 (102)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.80 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.20 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	16.78 (20.37)	5.82 (49)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.81 (0.19)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.19 (0.19)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	14.10 (22.68)	3.46 (30)	0.002
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.76 (0.26)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.24 (0.26)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	18.20 (20.93)	4.08 (21)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.81 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.19 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	11.37 (14.99)	7.70 (102)	<.001
STM	Con	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.77 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Con	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.23 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	5	Precision (κ)	13.66 (22.01)	5.30 (72)	<.001
STM	Rel	Colour	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.81 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Rel	Colour	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.19 (0.23)	—	—

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STM	Syn (all)	Location	1	Precision (κ)	38.72 (24.06)	16.17 (100)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.87 (0.13)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.13 (0.13)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	1	Precision (κ)	36.21 (23.79)	10.55 (47)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.88 (0.12)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.12 (0.12)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	1	Precision (κ)	45.23 (27.37)	9.20 (30)	<.001
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.87 (0.14)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.13 (0.14)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	1	Precision (κ)	35.01 (18.10)	9.07 (21)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.86 (0.12)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.14 (0.12)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	1	Precision (κ)	35.75 (25.43)	14.47 (105)	<.001
STM	Con	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.15)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.15)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	1	Precision (κ)	42.64 (31.19)	11.60 (71)	<.001
STM	Rel	Location	1	Target Prob (p_t)	0.86 (0.19)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	1	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.14 (0.19)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Location	3	Precision (κ)	35.39 (43.85)	8.07 (99)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.53 (0.24)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.47 (0.24)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	3	Precision (κ)	32.80 (40.03)	5.79 (49)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.58 (0.20)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.42 (0.20)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	3	Precision (κ)	27.68 (36.43)	4.09 (28)	<.001
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.51 (0.28)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.49 (0.28)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	3	Precision (κ)	52.22 (57.74)	4.14 (20)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.45 (0.25)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.55 (0.25)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	3	Precision (κ)	19.06 (24.10)	7.95 (100)	<.001
STM	Con	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.56 (0.28)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.44 (0.28)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	3	Precision (κ)	16.09 (26.65)	5.16 (72)	<.001
STM	Rel	Location	3	Target Prob (p_t)	0.71 (0.29)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	3	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.29 (0.29)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Location	5	Precision (κ)	37.13 (41.48)	9.04 (101)	<.001
STM	Syn (all)	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.63 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (all)	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.37 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	5	Precision (κ)	38.73 (47.05)	5.82 (49)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.64 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC)	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.36 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	5	Precision (κ)	38.50 (36.43)	5.88 (30)	<.001
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.62 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (SS)	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.38 (0.22)	—	—
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	5	Precision (κ)	31.28 (35.06)	4.09 (20)	<.001
STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.63 (0.23)	—	—

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STM	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.37 (0.23)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	5	Precision (κ)	39.45 (43.59)	9.18 (102)	<.001
STM	Con	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.62 (0.25)	—	—
STM	Con	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.38 (0.25)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	5	Precision (κ)	33.68 (30.65)	9.39 (72)	<.001
STM	Rel	Location	5	Target Prob (p_t)	0.71 (0.26)	—	—
STM	Rel	Location	5	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.29 (0.26)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	14.39 (18.75)	8.12 (111)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.82 (0.14)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.18 (0.14)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	13.08 (6.72)	14.69 (56)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.84 (0.12)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.16 (0.12)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	13.21 (14.65)	5.02 (30)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.80 (0.15)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.20 (0.15)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	19.05 (35.76)	2.61 (23)	0.016
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.16)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.16)	—	—
LTMI	Con	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	13.15 (20.93)	6.34 (101)	<.001
LTMI	Con	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.78 (0.15)	—	—
LTMI	Con	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.22 (0.15)	—	—
LTMI	Rel	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	10.69 (24.01)	3.86 (74)	<.001
LTMI	Rel	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.79 (0.17)	—	—
LTMI	Rel	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.21 (0.17)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (all)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	33.95 (23.38)	15.23 (109)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (all)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.91 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (all)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.09 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	33.65 (24.29)	10.18 (53)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.91 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.09 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	34.74 (23.53)	8.35 (31)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.91 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.09 (0.07)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	33.60 (22.02)	7.48 (23)	<.001
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.88 (0.08)	—	—
LTMI	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.12 (0.08)	—	—
LTMI	Con	Location	—	Precision (κ)	26.49 (15.43)	17.42 (102)	<.001
LTMI	Con	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.86 (0.11)	—	—
LTMI	Con	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.14 (0.11)	—	—
LTMI	Rel	Location	—	Precision (κ)	26.65 (56.00)	4.07 (72)	<.001
LTMI	Rel	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.90 (0.10)	—	—
LTMI	Rel	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.10 (0.10)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	9.40 (5.31)	17.88 (101)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.18)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (all)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.18)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	10.61 (5.64)	13.02 (47)	<.001

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LTMD	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.88 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.12 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	7.68 (4.61)	9.12 (29)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.76 (0.21)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.24 (0.21)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	9.13 (5.00)	8.95 (23)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Con	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	8.56 (5.90)	14.30 (96)	<.001
LTMD	Con	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.80 (0.22)	—	—
LTMD	Con	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.20 (0.22)	—	—
LTMD	Rel	Colour	—	Precision (κ)	5.03 (3.53)	11.99 (70)	<.001
LTMD	Rel	Colour	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.78 (0.23)	—	—
LTMD	Rel	Colour	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.22 (0.23)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (all)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	23.83 (23.13)	10.55 (104)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (all)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.84 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (all)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.16 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	25.90 (29.31)	6.31 (50)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.87 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.13 (0.16)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	19.61 (12.49)	8.60 (29)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.17)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.17)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Precision (κ)	24.69 (17.94)	6.74 (23)	<.001
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.80 (0.15)	—	—
LTMD	Syn (GC+SS)	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.20 (0.15)	—	—
LTMD	Con	Location	—	Precision (κ)	20.19 (14.50)	13.79 (97)	<.001
LTMD	Con	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.83 (0.17)	—	—
LTMD	Con	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.17 (0.17)	—	—
LTMD	Rel	Location	—	Precision (κ)	15.49 (13.09)	9.98 (70)	<.001
LTMD	Rel	Location	—	Target Prob (p_t)	0.84 (0.20)	—	—
LTMD	Rel	Location	—	Guess Rate (p_u)	0.16 (0.20)	—	—

Note. In the two-component model, higher precision (κ) reflects more precise target representations, higher target probability (p_t) reflects a greater proportion of target-based responses, and lower guess rate (p_u) reflects fewer random guesses

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Table 5

Summary of Bayesian Linear Models (Regression Equivalent), by Task

Model	Predictor	B (slope)	SE	t	p	BF	Interpretation
STM Analyses							
Within-Domain							
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour	1.23	0.11	10.78	<.001	1.39e+24	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	1.13	0.12	9.21	<.001	2.43e+17	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Synaesthesia	-1.91	0.85	-2.25	0.026		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Age	1.29	0.11	12.12	<.001	5.59e+30	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Age	0.01	0.03	0.37	0.709		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	1.25	0.11	10.91	<.001	5.87e+24	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	0.04	0.06	0.68	0.497		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	1.25	0.11	10.9	<.001	5.40e+24	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Identified Regulation	0.05	0.08	0.59	0.553		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + External Regulation	1.2	0.12	10.17	<.001	2.42e+21	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	External Regulation	0.11	0.07	1.5	0.135		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Amotivation	1.18	0.12	9.75	<.001	4.00e+19	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Amotivation	0.16	0.09	1.68	0.093		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	1.25	0.12	10.58	<.001	1.68e+23	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Imagery Ability	0.04	0.05	0.83	0.407		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	1.24	0.11	10.82	<.001	2.17e+24	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Technical Cognition	0.06	0.04	1.39	0.167		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Word Forms	1.22	0.12	10.09	<.001	1.07e+21	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Word Forms	-0.02	0.12	-0.14	0.885		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Organisation	1.24	0.11	10.8	<.001	1.71e+24	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Organisation	0.11	0.08	1.28	0.202		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Global Bias	1.23	0.12	10.59	<.001	1.95e+23	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Global Bias	0.02	0.15	0.12	0.903		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	1.23	0.11	10.73	<.001	7.91e+23	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →colour	Systemising Tendency	0.07	0.1	0.72	0.471		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location	0.16	0.07	2.5	0.013	2.61e+00	Inconclusive

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Synaesthesia	0.1	0.07	1.51	0.133	3.57e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Synaesthesia	-0.96	0.38	-2.52	0.012		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Age	0.2	0.06	3.12	0.002	1.61e+01	Strong (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Age	0.03	0.02	1.52	0.131		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	0.17	0.07	2.56	0.011	3.09e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Intrinsic Motivation	0	0.03	0.06	0.952		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Identified Regulation	0.17	0.07	2.55	0.011	3.04e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Identified Regulation	0	0.04	-0.1	0.917		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + External Regulation	0.18	0.07	2.67	0.008	4.23e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	External Regulation	-0.02	0.03	-0.74	0.462		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Amotivation	0.19	0.07	2.74	0.007	5.27e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Amotivation	-0.04	0.04	-0.97	0.332		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Imagery Ability	0.16	0.07	2.34	0.02	1.90e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Imagery Ability	-0.01	0.02	-0.25	0.802		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Technical Cognition	0.15	0.07	2.22	0.027	1.38e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Technical Cognition	-0.04	0.02	-2.16	0.032		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Word Forms	0.17	0.07	2.31	0.022	1.86e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Word Forms	0	0.06	0.05	0.957		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Organisation	0.18	0.07	2.68	0.008	4.23e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Organisation	0.05	0.04	1.27	0.206		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Global Bias	0.18	0.07	2.66	0.008	4.12e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Global Bias	0.05	0.07	0.79	0.429		
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	0.16	0.07	2.48	0.014	2.55e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP location →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.04	0.05	-0.81	0.419		
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Cross-Domain							
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour	0.08	0.05	1.55	0.122	3.55e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	0.02	0.06	0.39	0.698	8.34e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Synaesthesia	-1.1	0.39	-2.83	0.005		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Age	0.1	0.05	1.91	0.057	7.40e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Age	0.02	0.02	1.05	0.297		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	0.08	0.05	1.61	0.109	3.92e-01	Inconclusive

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Intrinsic Motivation	0	0.03	-0.01	0.989		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	0.08	0.05	1.6	0.11	3.89e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Identified Regulation	-0.01	0.04	-0.14	0.89		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + External Regulation	0.09	0.05	1.68	0.095	4.56e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	External Regulation	-0.02	0.03	-0.46	0.646		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Amotivation	0.1	0.06	1.74	0.082	5.30e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Amotivation	-0.03	0.04	-0.67	0.501		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	0.07	0.05	1.38	0.17	2.77e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Imagery Ability	-0.01	0.02	-0.64	0.523		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	0.07	0.05	1.35	0.177	2.58e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Technical Cognition	-0.04	0.02	-2.34	0.02		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Word Forms	0.07	0.06	1.32	0.189	2.58e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Word Forms	-0.03	0.06	-0.58	0.564		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Organisation	0.09	0.05	1.68	0.095	4.43e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Organisation	0.04	0.04	1.1	0.27		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Global Bias	0.09	0.05	1.63	0.105	4.10e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Global Bias	0.03	0.07	0.42	0.676		
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	0.08	0.05	1.51	0.132	3.33e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 1): VP colour →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.04	0.05	-0.85	0.395		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location	1.28	0.15	8.34	<.001	1.17e+14	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Synaesthesia	1.11	0.16	6.91	<.001	2.30e+09	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Synaesthesia	-2.75	0.89	-3.1	0.002		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Age	1.35	0.14	9.33	<.001	6.93e+17	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Age	0.04	0.04	1.12	0.265		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	1.3	0.15	8.43	<.001	2.48e+14	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	0.04	0.07	0.63	0.531		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Identified Regulation	1.3	0.15	8.41	<.001	2.20e+14	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Identified Regulation	0.04	0.09	0.46	0.644		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + External Regulation	1.22	0.16	7.67	<.001	5.71e+11	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	External Regulation	0.14	0.08	1.8	0.073		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Amotivation	1.18	0.16	7.3	<.001	3.80e+10	Decisive (effect)

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STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Amotivation	0.23	0.1	2.3	0.023		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Imagery Ability	1.32	0.16	8.11	<.001	1.95e+13	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Imagery Ability	0.05	0.05	0.85	0.395		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Technical Cognition	1.31	0.16	8.41	<.001	2.11e+14	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Technical Cognition	0.07	0.04	1.49	0.136		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Word Forms	1.3	0.17	7.56	<.001	2.59e+11	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Word Forms	0.04	0.14	0.32	0.75		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Organisation	1.3	0.16	8.36	<.001	1.38e+14	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Organisation	0.12	0.09	1.27	0.206		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Global Bias	1.3	0.16	8.15	<.001	2.63e+13	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Global Bias	0.09	0.16	0.57	0.571		
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	1.28	0.16	8.25	<.001	5.82e+13	Decisive (effect)
STM (Load 1): VP location →colour	Systemising Tendency	0.05	0.11	0.44	0.661		
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Within-Domain							
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour	0.42	0.28	1.49	0.136	4.17e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	0.24	0.3	0.81	0.421	1.74e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Synaesthesia	-3.3	2.14	-1.54	0.125		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Age	0.61	0.28	2.15	0.033	1.44e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Age	0.41	0.09	4.3	<.001		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	0.39	0.28	1.37	0.171	3.46e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.16	0.16	-1.03	0.305		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	0.4	0.28	1.41	0.16	3.66e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.08	0.21	-0.4	0.69		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + External Regulation	0.44	0.29	1.5	0.136	4.33e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	External Regulation	-0.08	0.19	-0.42	0.675		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Amotivation	0.38	0.3	1.3	0.196	3.25e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Amotivation	0.05	0.24	0.21	0.83		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	0.44	0.29	1.52	0.131	4.50e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Imagery Ability	0.07	0.12	0.58	0.56		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	0.33	0.28	1.17	0.244	2.55e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.21	0.1	-2	0.047		

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STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Word Forms	0.33	0.3	1.12	0.263	2.53e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Word Forms	-0.2	0.3	-0.65	0.514		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Organisation	0.4	0.28	1.41	0.161	3.63e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Organisation	0.01	0.21	0.03	0.972		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Global Bias	0.42	0.28	1.48	0.14	4.13e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Global Bias	0.2	0.36	0.55	0.585		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	0.36	0.28	1.28	0.203	2.98e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP colour →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.37	0.26	-1.42	0.156		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location	0.07	0.27	0.26	0.797	1.07e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Synaesthesia	-0.06	0.29	-0.2	0.843	7.89e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Synaesthesia	-2.06	1.61	-1.28	0.202		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Age	0.26	0.28	0.92	0.358	2.18e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Age	0.22	0.07	2.93	0.004		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	0.04	0.27	0.15	0.88	9.66e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.02	0.12	-0.13	0.899		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Identified Regulation	0.05	0.27	0.19	0.848	9.98e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Identified Regulation	0.11	0.15	0.73	0.468		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + External Regulation	0	0.28	-0.01	0.996	8.80e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	External Regulation	0.09	0.14	0.6	0.547		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Amotivation	-0.03	0.28	-0.12	0.904	8.16e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Amotivation	0.16	0.18	0.89	0.375		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Imagery Ability	0.06	0.29	0.21	0.835	1.08e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Imagery Ability	0.01	0.1	0.11	0.914		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Technical Cognition	-0.03	0.28	-0.13	0.899	7.88e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Technical Cognition	-0.16	0.08	-2.1	0.037		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Word Forms	0.02	0.3	0.06	0.952	9.98e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Word Forms	-0.06	0.24	-0.25	0.8		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Organisation	0.04	0.28	0.13	0.895	9.66e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Organisation	-0.08	0.16	-0.5	0.615		
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Global Bias	0.15	0.28	0.53	0.596	1.42e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Global Bias	0.41	0.28	1.45	0.149		

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

STM (Load 3): VP location →location	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	0.04	0.28	0.15	0.877	9.82e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.09	0.2	-0.44	0.663		
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Cross-Domain							
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour	-0.11	0.21	-0.5	0.617	5.35e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	-0.25	0.23	-1.07	0.285	4.12e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Synaesthesia	-2.6	1.63	-1.6	0.11		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Age	-0.03	0.22	-0.15	0.88	7.10e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Age	0.2	0.07	2.74	0.007		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	-0.13	0.21	-0.63	0.527	4.88e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.02	0.12	-0.18	0.859		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	-0.12	0.21	-0.58	0.564	5.05e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Identified Regulation	0.1	0.15	0.68	0.497		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + External Regulation	-0.18	0.22	-0.81	0.421	4.52e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	External Regulation	0.11	0.14	0.81	0.421		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Amotivation	-0.21	0.22	-0.95	0.341	4.23e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Amotivation	0.21	0.18	1.15	0.251		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	-0.13	0.22	-0.56	0.575	5.40e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Imagery Ability	-0.01	0.09	-0.12	0.906		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	-0.17	0.21	-0.82	0.415	4.40e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Technical Cognition	-0.17	0.08	-2.19	0.029		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Word Forms	-0.15	0.23	-0.69	0.493	5.05e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Word Forms	-0.12	0.23	-0.51	0.609		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Organisation	-0.13	0.21	-0.6	0.552	5.06e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Organisation	-0.09	0.16	-0.57	0.571		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Global Bias	-0.07	0.22	-0.33	0.744	6.12e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Global Bias	0.36	0.28	1.28	0.201		
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	-0.13	0.21	-0.59	0.553	5.07e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 3): VP colour →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.1	0.2	-0.5	0.617		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location	0.42	0.36	1.15	0.251	2.63e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Synaesthesia	0.19	0.38	0.5	0.618	1.28e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Synaesthesia	-3.59	2.12	-1.7	0.091		

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STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Age	0.79	0.36	2.17	0.031	1.61e+00	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Age	0.43	0.1	4.43	<.001		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	0.36	0.36	1	0.317	2.17e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.17	0.16	-1.04	0.301		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Identified Regulation	0.39	0.36	1.06	0.29	2.33e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.09	0.21	-0.45	0.657		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + External Regulation	0.43	0.38	1.13	0.258	2.67e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	External Regulation	-0.07	0.19	-0.35	0.728		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Amotivation	0.35	0.38	0.92	0.356	2.06e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Amotivation	0.08	0.24	0.34	0.737		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Imagery Ability	0.43	0.38	1.13	0.262	2.67e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Imagery Ability	0.06	0.13	0.5	0.619		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Technical Cognition	0.26	0.36	0.72	0.473	1.53e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.21	0.1	-2.02	0.044		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Word Forms	0.25	0.4	0.63	0.53	1.52e-01	Substantial (null)
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Word Forms	-0.23	0.32	-0.71	0.48		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Organisation	0.37	0.36	1.02	0.31	2.21e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Organisation	0	0.21	0.02	0.982		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Global Bias	0.42	0.37	1.13	0.261	2.62e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Global Bias	0.21	0.37	0.56	0.573		
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	0.33	0.36	0.92	0.356	1.95e-01	Inconclusive
STM (Load 3): VP location →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.38	0.26	-1.48	0.14		
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Within-Domain							
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour	-0.54	0.4	-1.36	0.175	3.39e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	-0.62	0.43	-1.42	0.156	3.57e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Synaesthesia	-1.37	3.07	-0.44	0.657		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Age	-0.14	0.4	-0.35	0.728	6.09e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Age	0.66	0.13	5.04	<.001		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	-0.6	0.4	-1.49	0.137	3.18e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.02	0.23	-0.11	0.914		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	-0.6	0.4	-1.5	0.134	3.17e-02	Very strong (null)

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STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.06	0.29	-0.22	0.826		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + External Regulation	-0.39	0.41	-0.96	0.336	4.26e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	External Regulation	-0.52	0.27	-1.97	0.05		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Amotivation	-0.4	0.42	-0.95	0.345	4.42e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Amotivation	-0.5	0.34	-1.46	0.145		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	-0.64	0.42	-1.52	0.129	3.30e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.1	0.18	-0.56	0.579		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	-0.65	0.4	-1.62	0.106	3.02e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.22	0.14	-1.54	0.125		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Word Forms	-0.45	0.42	-1.07	0.286	4.17e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Word Forms	0.36	0.43	0.83	0.405		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Organisation	-0.56	0.4	-1.39	0.165	3.35e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Organisation	0.08	0.3	0.27	0.788		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Global Bias	-0.49	0.41	-1.22	0.223	3.68e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Global Bias	0.6	0.52	1.16	0.248		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	-0.59	0.4	-1.46	0.146	3.25e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.17	0.37	-0.46	0.645		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location	-1.38	0.47	-2.98	0.003	1.94e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Synaesthesia	-1.46	0.5	-2.93	0.004	2.12e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Synaesthesia	-1.16	2.74	-0.42	0.673		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Age	-0.81	0.47	-1.74	0.084	3.06e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Age	0.55	0.12	4.55	<.001		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	-1.44	0.46	-3.11	0.002	1.86e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.17	0.2	-0.83	0.407		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Identified Regulation	-1.43	0.46	-3.08	0.002	1.87e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Identified Regulation	-0.14	0.26	-0.54	0.59		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + External Regulation	-1.21	0.48	-2.53	0.012	2.31e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	External Regulation	-0.4	0.24	-1.67	0.096		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Amotivation	-1.32	0.49	-2.71	0.007	2.22e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Amotivation	-0.2	0.31	-0.66	0.51		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Imagery Ability	-1.49	0.5	-3.01	0.003	2.06e-02	Very strong (null)

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Imagery Ability	-0.11	0.16	-0.66	0.508		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Technical Cognition	-1.6	0.47	-3.4	<.001	1.73e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Technical Cognition	-0.34	0.13	-2.6	0.01		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Word Forms	-1.62	0.52	-3.12	0.002	2.11e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Word Forms	-0.42	0.41	-1.05	0.297		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Organisation	-1.41	0.47	-3	0.003	1.96e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Organisation	-0.15	0.27	-0.53	0.594		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Global Bias	-1.38	0.48	-2.86	0.005	2.10e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Global Bias	0	0.48	0.01	0.993		
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	-1.42	0.47	-3.04	0.003	1.92e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.33	0.33	-1.01	0.312		
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Cross-Domain							
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour	-0.95	0.36	-2.64	0.009	2.03e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	-1.01	0.39	-2.58	0.01	2.25e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Synaesthesia	-1.05	2.78	-0.38	0.705		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Age	-0.62	0.36	-1.72	0.086	2.88e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Age	0.57	0.12	4.82	<.001		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	-1.02	0.36	-2.82	0.005	1.90e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.16	0.21	-0.79	0.429		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	-1.01	0.36	-2.81	0.005	1.91e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Identified Regulation	-0.15	0.26	-0.58	0.565		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + External Regulation	-0.83	0.37	-2.26	0.025	2.38e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	External Regulation	-0.43	0.24	-1.77	0.078		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Amotivation	-0.91	0.38	-2.4	0.017	2.33e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Amotivation	-0.22	0.31	-0.71	0.481		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	-1	0.38	-2.63	0.009	2.15e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Imagery Ability	-0.07	0.16	-0.45	0.656		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	-1.07	0.36	-2.95	0.003	1.83e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Technical Cognition	-0.31	0.13	-2.4	0.017		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Word Forms	-1.02	0.38	-2.65	0.009	2.16e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Word Forms	-0.2	0.39	-0.52	0.603		

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Organisation	-0.96	0.36	-2.64	0.009	2.04e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Organisation	-0.11	0.27	-0.41	0.681		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Global Bias	-0.93	0.37	-2.54	0.012	2.14e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Global Bias	0.14	0.47	0.3	0.764		
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	-0.99	0.36	-2.71	0.007	1.99e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP colour →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.33	0.33	-1.01	0.313		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location	-1.09	0.51	-2.13	0.035	2.98e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Synaesthesia	-1.23	0.55	-2.23	0.027	3.07e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Synaesthesia	-2.07	3.02	-0.69	0.493		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Age	-0.41	0.51	-0.8	0.427	5.25e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Age	0.64	0.13	4.8	<.001		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	-1.15	0.51	-2.23	0.027	2.89e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.04	0.23	-0.17	0.864		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Identified Regulation	-1.15	0.51	-2.23	0.027	2.88e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.07	0.28	-0.24	0.812		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + External Regulation	-0.9	0.53	-1.7	0.091	3.57e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	External Regulation	-0.47	0.27	-1.77	0.078		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Amotivation	-0.93	0.54	-1.74	0.084	3.57e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Amotivation	-0.43	0.34	-1.25	0.213		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Imagery Ability	-1.31	0.55	-2.4	0.017	2.89e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.16	0.18	-0.9	0.37		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Technical Cognition	-1.31	0.52	-2.51	0.013	2.67e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.26	0.14	-1.76	0.079		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Word Forms	-1.07	0.57	-1.86	0.064	3.64e-02	Strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Word Forms	0.14	0.45	0.31	0.757		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Organisation	-1.14	0.52	-2.19	0.029	2.94e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Organisation	0.04	0.3	0.14	0.891		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Global Bias	-1.04	0.53	-1.95	0.052	3.26e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Global Bias	0.45	0.52	0.87	0.387		
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	-1.17	0.52	-2.26	0.025	2.87e-02	Very strong (null)
STM (Load 5): VP location →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.19	0.36	-0.52	0.606		

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

LTMI Analyses

Within-Domain

LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour	1.19	0.21	5.68	<.001	1.27e+06	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	0.94	0.22	4.21	<.001	9.89e+02	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Synaesthesia	-4.6	1.62	-2.83	0.005		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Age	1.35	0.2	6.6	<.001	3.42e+08	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Age	0.32	0.07	4.54	<.001		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	1.15	0.21	5.52	<.001	5.27e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.24	0.14	-1.75	0.081		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	1.16	0.21	5.53	<.001	5.56e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.22	0.16	-1.42	0.157		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + External Regulation	1.17	0.22	5.21	<.001	1.05e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	External Regulation	0	0.17	0.02	0.983		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Amotivation	1.08	0.22	4.92	<.001	2.40e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Amotivation	0.26	0.2	1.27	0.205		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	1.1	0.22	5.01	<.001	3.69e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.19	0.1	-1.94	0.054		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	1.18	0.21	5.5	<.001	4.74e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.1	0.08	-1.19	0.234		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Word Forms	1.12	0.22	5.05	<.001	4.55e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Word Forms	-0.32	0.23	-1.38	0.168		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Organisation	1.2	0.21	5.61	<.001	8.53e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Organisation	-0.08	0.17	-0.46	0.647		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Global Bias	1.14	0.21	5.35	<.001	2.12e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Global Bias	-0.56	0.28	-2.02	0.045		
LTMI: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	1.19	0.21	5.59	<.001	7.85e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP colour →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.3	0.2	-1.47	0.144		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location	0.19	0.19	0.99	0.324	1.82e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Synaesthesia	-0.03	0.2	-0.15	0.879	6.09e-02	Strong (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Synaesthesia	-3.43	1.1	-3.13	0.002		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Age	0.42	0.19	2.23	0.027	1.56e+00	Inconclusive

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

LTMI: VP location →location	Age	0.24	0.05	4.83	<.001		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	0.16	0.19	0.86	0.391	1.53e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.2	0.09	-2.14	0.034		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Identified Regulation	0.17	0.19	0.87	0.383	1.56e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Identified Regulation	-0.12	0.11	-1.11	0.269		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + External Regulation	0.15	0.2	0.76	0.451	1.45e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	External Regulation	0.03	0.11	0.27	0.787		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Amotivation	0.09	0.2	0.46	0.645	1.05e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Amotivation	0.16	0.14	1.14	0.254		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Imagery Ability	0.15	0.2	0.76	0.451	1.44e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Imagery Ability	-0.08	0.07	-1.25	0.211		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Technical Cognition	0.16	0.19	0.83	0.407	1.50e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Technical Cognition	-0.12	0.05	-2.25	0.025		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Word Forms	0.17	0.21	0.78	0.436	1.56e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Word Forms	-0.11	0.17	-0.68	0.5		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Organisation	0.23	0.19	1.2	0.232	2.44e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP location →location	Organisation	0.04	0.11	0.38	0.706		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Global Bias	0.16	0.2	0.81	0.418	1.50e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP location →location	Global Bias	-0.29	0.19	-1.52	0.13		
LTMI: VP location →location	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	0.22	0.19	1.16	0.248	2.30e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP location →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.05	0.14	-0.33	0.738		
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Cross-Domain							
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour	0.15	0.14	1.07	0.284	1.88e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	-0.03	0.15	-0.19	0.846	5.81e-02	Strong (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	Synaesthesia	-3.46	1.11	-3.1	0.002		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Age	0.27	0.14	1.91	0.058	7.09e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Age	0.23	0.05	4.66	<.001		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	0.12	0.14	0.87	0.386	1.44e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.2	0.09	-2.11	0.036		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	0.13	0.14	0.92	0.36	1.53e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	Identified Regulation	-0.12	0.11	-1.08	0.28		

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + External Regulation	0.13	0.15	0.82	0.41	1.47e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	External Regulation	0.03	0.11	0.23	0.821		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Amotivation	0.09	0.15	0.57	0.572	1.09e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	Amotivation	0.16	0.14	1.13	0.258		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	0.14	0.15	0.91	0.363	1.58e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMI: VP colour →location	Imagery Ability	-0.08	0.07	-1.27	0.206		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	0.15	0.14	1.05	0.294	1.83e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Technical Cognition	-0.13	0.05	-2.29	0.023		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Word Forms	0.15	0.15	1	0.319	1.78e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Word Forms	-0.13	0.16	-0.79	0.431		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Organisation	0.18	0.14	1.27	0.204	2.49e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Organisation	0.04	0.11	0.32	0.748		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Global Bias	0.15	0.15	1.05	0.297	1.83e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Global Bias	-0.3	0.19	-1.59	0.113		
LTMI: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	0.18	0.14	1.25	0.213	2.41e-01	Inconclusive
LTMI: VP colour →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.05	0.14	-0.34	0.738		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location	1.34	0.28	4.73	<.001	1.04e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Synaesthesia	1	0.3	3.37	<.001	4.44e+01	Very strong (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Synaesthesia	-5.34	1.62	-3.3	0.001		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Age	1.69	0.28	6.01	<.001	9.61e+06	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Age	0.35	0.07	4.83	<.001		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	1.3	0.28	4.61	<.001	5.72e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.26	0.14	-1.9	0.058		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Identified Regulation	1.3	0.28	4.6	<.001	5.53e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.25	0.16	-1.55	0.122		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + External Regulation	1.27	0.3	4.2	<.001	1.01e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	External Regulation	0.08	0.17	0.45	0.652		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Amotivation	1.17	0.3	3.88	<.001	2.80e+02	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Amotivation	0.3	0.21	1.44	0.152		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Imagery Ability	1.19	0.3	3.94	<.001	3.62e+02	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.19	0.1	-1.93	0.055		

PERCEPTION AND MEMORY IN SPECIAL POPULATIONS

LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Technical Cognition	1.31	0.29	4.49	<.001	3.42e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.08	0.08	-1	0.321		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Word Forms	1.23	0.32	3.86	<.001	2.77e+02	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Word Forms	-0.24	0.25	-0.94	0.346		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Organisation	1.35	0.29	4.64	<.001	6.96e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Organisation	-0.04	0.17	-0.25	0.804		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Global Bias	1.24	0.3	4.21	<.001	1.07e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Global Bias	-0.49	0.29	-1.7	0.091		
LTMI: VP location →colour	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	1.34	0.29	4.64	<.001	6.82e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMI: VP location →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.3	0.21	-1.45	0.148		
LTMD Analyses							
Within-Domain							
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour	1.46	0.27	5.43	<.001	3.29e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	1.26	0.29	4.33	<.001	1.71e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Synaesthesia	-3.93	2.17	-1.81	0.072		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Age	1.71	0.27	6.25	<.001	4.04e+07	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Age	0.4	0.09	4.32	<.001		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	1.42	0.27	5.31	<.001	1.75e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.24	0.16	-1.47	0.143		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	1.41	0.27	5.23	<.001	1.16e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.18	0.19	-0.97	0.333		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + External Regulation	1.38	0.28	4.96	<.001	2.94e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	External Regulation	0.15	0.2	0.74	0.461		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Amotivation	1.15	0.28	4.1	<.001	6.24e+02	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Amotivation	0.82	0.27	3.03	0.003		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	1.36	0.28	4.82	<.001	1.55e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.17	0.13	-1.35	0.179		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	1.45	0.27	5.27	<.001	1.44e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Technical Cognition	-0.03	0.11	-0.24	0.812		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Word Forms	1.33	0.28	4.68	<.001	7.91e+03	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Word Forms	-0.45	0.31	-1.48	0.141		

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LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Organisation	1.48	0.27	5.4	<.001	2.91e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Organisation	0.24	0.22	1.1	0.273		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Global Bias	1.43	0.27	5.21	<.001	1.05e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Global Bias	-0.28	0.37	-0.77	0.441		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	1.44	0.27	5.28	<.001	1.51e+05	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.24	0.26	-0.92	0.359		
LTMD: VP colour →colour	VP Colour + LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	1.41	0.28	5.11	<.001	6.20e+04	Decisive (effect)
LTMD: VP colour →colour	LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0	0	0.09	0.932		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location	0.11	0.34	0.31	0.756	9.93e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Synaesthesia	-0.09	0.36	-0.24	0.808	6.71e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Synaesthesia	-3	2.02	-1.49	0.138		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Age	0.52	0.34	1.51	0.133	4.53e-01	Inconclusive
LTMD: VP location →location	Age	0.41	0.09	4.6	<.001		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	0.06	0.34	0.16	0.87	8.73e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.22	0.16	-1.39	0.166		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Identified Regulation	0.04	0.34	0.12	0.905	8.45e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Identified Regulation	-0.18	0.18	-1.02	0.31		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + External Regulation	0.07	0.36	0.2	0.84	9.59e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	External Regulation	0	0.19	0.01	0.991		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Amotivation	-0.27	0.36	-0.74	0.46	4.83e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Amotivation	0.67	0.26	2.55	0.011		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Imagery Ability	0.09	0.36	0.26	0.796	9.96e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Imagery Ability	-0.04	0.12	-0.35	0.73		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Technical Cognition	0.1	0.34	0.29	0.774	9.84e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Technical Cognition	-0.06	0.1	-0.59	0.554		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Word Forms	-0.11	0.37	-0.29	0.774	6.71e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Word Forms	-0.44	0.3	-1.48	0.14		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Organisation	0.17	0.34	0.51	0.611	1.21e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Organisation	0.22	0.2	1.07	0.286		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Global Bias	0.11	0.35	0.3	0.763	1.01e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Global Bias	-0.12	0.35	-0.34	0.731		

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LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	0.1	0.34	0.29	0.773	9.70e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.39	0.24	-1.62	0.107		
LTMD: VP location →location	VP Location + LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0.06	0.34	0.18	0.858	8.95e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP location →location	LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0	0	0.95	0.344		
<hr/>							
Cross-Domain							
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour	0.11	0.25	0.42	0.676	9.89e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Synaesthesia	-0.05	0.27	-0.17	0.863	6.42e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Synaesthesia	-2.96	2.04	-1.45	0.148		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Age	0.31	0.26	1.23	0.221	2.64e-01	Inconclusive
LTMD: VP colour →location	Age	0.39	0.09	4.5	<.001		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Intrinsic Motivation	0.06	0.25	0.25	0.803	8.48e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.22	0.16	-1.38	0.17		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Identified Regulation	0.05	0.26	0.21	0.836	8.23e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Identified Regulation	-0.18	0.18	-1	0.32		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + External Regulation	0.09	0.27	0.34	0.738	9.62e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	External Regulation	0	0.19	-0.02	0.984		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Amotivation	-0.14	0.27	-0.54	0.591	4.87e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Amotivation	0.64	0.26	2.48	0.014		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Imagery Ability	0.1	0.26	0.37	0.709	9.79e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Imagery Ability	-0.04	0.12	-0.34	0.736		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Technical Cognition	0.1	0.25	0.41	0.681	9.87e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Technical Cognition	-0.06	0.1	-0.6	0.549		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Word Forms	0.01	0.26	0.04	0.969	7.31e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Word Forms	-0.4	0.28	-1.43	0.155		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Organisation	0.14	0.25	0.56	0.578	1.14e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Organisation	0.21	0.2	1.06	0.292		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Global Bias	0.11	0.25	0.43	0.666	1.01e-01	Substantial (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Global Bias	-0.13	0.34	-0.37	0.713		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + Systemising Tendency	0.1	0.25	0.4	0.69	9.67e-02	Strong (null)
LTMD: VP colour →location	Systemising Tendency	-0.39	0.24	-1.62	0.107		
LTMD: VP colour →location	VP Colour + LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0.07	0.26	0.28	0.781	8.97e-02	Strong (null)

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LTMD: VP colour →location	LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0	0	0.89	0.376			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location	1.84	0.36	5.04	<.001	4.79e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Synaesthesia	1.55	0.39	3.99	<.001	4.57e+02	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Synaesthesia	-4.47	2.16	-2.07	0.039			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Age	2.3	0.37	6.26	<.001	4.49e+07	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Age	0.45	0.09	4.78	<.001			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Intrinsic Motivation	1.77	0.36	4.9	<.001	2.35e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.27	0.16	-1.63	0.105			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Identified Regulation	1.75	0.36	4.82	<.001	1.58e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Identified Regulation	-0.23	0.19	-1.21	0.228			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + External Regulation	1.7	0.38	4.45	<.001	3.08e+03	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	External Regulation	0.14	0.2	0.71	0.481			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Amotivation	1.35	0.38	3.54	<.001	8.19e+01	Very strong (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Amotivation	0.85	0.28	3.08	0.002			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Imagery Ability	1.69	0.39	4.35	<.001	2.05e+03	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Imagery Ability	-0.15	0.13	-1.17	0.244			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Technical Cognition	1.83	0.37	4.88	<.001	2.24e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Technical Cognition	0	0.11	0	0.997			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Word Forms	1.67	0.41	4.08	<.001	6.82e+02	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Word Forms	-0.3	0.33	-0.91	0.363			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Organisation	1.89	0.37	5.08	<.001	5.80e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Organisation	0.28	0.22	1.27	0.204			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Global Bias	1.81	0.38	4.77	<.001	1.30e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Global Bias	-0.11	0.38	-0.3	0.764			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + Systemising Tendency	1.81	0.37	4.89	<.001	2.30e+04	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	Systemising Tendency	-0.23	0.26	-0.87	0.385			
LTMD: VP location →colour	VP Location + LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	1.72	0.37	4.68	<.001	8.51e+03	Decisive (effect)	
LTMD: VP location →colour	LTMI-LTMD Gap (hours)	0	0	0.68	0.498			

Note: Bayes Factor (BF) interpretations based on 1/6 and 6 sensitivity thresholds. For BF ≥ 6 (evidence for effect): 6-10 = Substantial, 10-30 = Strong, 30-100 = Very Strong, >100 = Decisive. For BF < 1/6 (evidence for null hypothesis): 0.10-0.167 = Substantial, 0.033-0.10 = Strong, 0.01-0.033 = Very Strong, <0.01 = Decisive. Values between 1/6 (0.167) and 6 are considered Inconclusive.

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Table 6

Univariate Effect Sizes (Cohen's d) Between Groups

Variable	Syn vs Con	Rel vs Con	Syn vs Rel
Imagery ability	0.50	-0.42	1.01
Technical cognition	0.41	0.28	0.14
Word forms	0.23	-0.37	0.58
Organisation	-0.04	-0.19	0.16
Global bias	0.10	-0.37	0.45
Systemising tendency	0.43	0.06	0.38
VP colour accuracy	0.63	-0.72	1.18
VP location accuracy	0.74	-0.69	1.03
STM colour accuracy	0.33	0.34	-0.03
STM location accuracy	0.23	0.50	-0.31
LTMI colour accuracy	0.37	-0.29	0.71
LTMI location accuracy	0.41	0.07	0.40
LTMD colour accuracy	0.26	-0.27	0.55
LTMD location accuracy	0.20	0.01	0.19

Note. Positive values indicate higher scores/performance in the first group.

Table 7

Correlations between Number of Synaesthesia Types and Task Performance

Task	Condition	Load	r	p	N
VP	Colour	—	-0.079	0.433	102
VP	Location	—	0.111	0.264	104
STM	Colour	1	0.028	0.784	101
STM	Location	1	0.076	0.448	102
STM	Colour	3	0.046	0.649	101
STM	Location	3	0.057	0.569	101
STM	Colour	5	-0.111	0.264	104
STM	Location	5	-0.099	0.320	103
LTMI	Colour	—	-0.039	0.684	112
LTMI	Location	—	-0.026	0.788	110
LTMD	Colour	—	-0.127	0.198	104
LTMD	Location	—	-0.053	0.594	102

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Table 8

Bayesian Group Comparisons of Few-Types and Many-Types Synaesthetes (based on Median Split)

Task	Group Comparison	Condition	Load	M1	M2	t(df)	p	BF	Interpretation
VP	Few types vs Many types	Colour	—	3.78	3.89	-0.33 (67.75)	0.740	0.11	Substantial (null)
VP	Few types vs Many types	Location	—	2.49	2.86	-1.46 (71.99)	0.149	0.46	Inconclusive
STM	Few types vs Many types	Colour	1	11.54	12.66	-1.23 (61.59)	0.224	0.27	Inconclusive
STM	Few types vs Many types	Location	1	5.18	5.31	-0.28 (72.14)	0.783	0.11	Substantial (null)
STM	Few types vs Many types	Colour	3	30.64	33.78	-0.98 (69.14)	0.329	0.26	Inconclusive
STM	Few types vs Many types	Location	3	18.37	19.26	-0.39 (64.21)	0.700	0.16	Substantial (null)
STM	Few types vs Many types	Colour	5	52.15	49.41	0.70 (84.59)	0.489	0.05	Strong (null)
STM	Few types vs Many types	Location	5	42.27	40.65	0.45 (79.31)	0.656	0.07	Strong (null)
LTMI	Few types vs Many types	Colour	—	28.15	28.67	-0.22 (85.07)	0.828	0.10s	Strong (null)
LTMI	Few types vs Many types	Location	—	16.80	15.69	0.82 (94.46)	0.416	0.05	Strong (null)
LTMD	Few types vs Many types	Colour	—	29.59	27.33	0.71 (96.46)	0.480	0.07	Strong (null)
LTMD	Few types vs Many types	Location	—	21.94	20.76	0.44 (90.82)	0.658	0.09	Strong (null)

Note. Median split: few synaesthesia types ≤ 3 ; many ≥ 4 .

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Table 9

T-tests of Model Estimates of Precision (kappa) in Few-Types and Many-Types Synaesthetes (based on Median Split)

Task	Condition	Load	Few Types: Kappa M (SD)	Many Types: Kappa M (SD)	t(df)	p
VP	Colour	—	224.63 (150.35)	183.55 (115.27)	1.54 (93)	0.126
VP	Location	—	387.04 (231.89)	349.02 (243.09)	0.79 (79)	0.429
STM	Colour	1	25.64 (16.44)	21.73 (12.43)	1.34 (90)	0.182
STM	Location	1	111.60 (92.42)	106.17 (93.97)	0.28 (69)	0.783
STM	Colour	3	17.17 (23.18)	14.69 (16.78)	0.63 (94)	0.533
STM	Location	3	41.17 (27.64)	34.29 (15.02)	1.62 (99)	0.108
STM	Colour	5	36.54 (44.23)	33.44 (43.73)	0.34 (76)	0.735
STM	Location	5	33.86 (43.69)	40.39 (39.30)	-0.79 (99)	0.429
LTMI	Colour	—	12.72 (7.80)	17.19 (28.93)	-0.98 (45)	0.333
LTMI	Location	—	34.05 (24.78)	33.79 (21.01)	0.06 (93)	0.954
LTMD	Colour	—	9.20 (5.05)	9.73 (5.75)	-0.47 (73)	0.637
LTMD	Location	—	23.75 (26.70)	23.95 (16.04)	-0.05 (103)	0.963

Note. Median split: few synaesthesia types ≤ 3 ; many ≥ 4 .

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Table 10

Analysis Plan

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling plan	Analysis Plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
1. Do synaesthetes demonstrate enhanced visual perception and memory advantages compared to non-synaesthetes?	Synaesthetes will display enhanced visual perception and memory advantages relative to non-synaesthetes. Specifically, this should manifest itself as more precision in the choice of colours and locations across multiple tasks (perception, short-term memory, long-term memory).	Power analysis: N=100 synaesthetes N= 100 non-synaesthetic "controls" N = 61 non-synaesthetic "relatives"	Mixed-factorial Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the within-subject factor Condition (colour vs. location recall) and the between-subject factor Group (synaesthetes vs. non-synaesthetes) and, as appropriate, the within-subject factor of array size (short-term memory) or block number (long-term memory).	Relevant effect sizes for statistical power analyses were based on effect sizes from Ovalle-Fresa et al. (2021) which uses a similar paradigm. For long-term memory, the value ($d=0.61$) was selected based on a meta-analysis by Ward et al., (2019).	If synaesthetes perform better on both perception and memory tasks, it would support an enhanced perception account as advantages go beyond dual-coding. Co-occurring performance differences across tasks would support representational accounts of memory.	Dual-coding and/or enhanced processing accounts of synaesthesia Representational accounts of cognitive processes.
2a. Is there a significant correlation between individual differences in performance on perceptual tasks and memory tasks?	Individual differences in performance on perceptual tasks will predict performance on the memory	As above.	Correlations between performance measures on the visual perception and memory tasks across all participants considering	As above.	Co-occurring performance differences across tasks would support representational accounts of memory.	Representational accounts of cognitive processes.

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tasks. Specifically, significant correlations should be observed between the precision of perception (of colour and location) and the corresponding visual characteristics when presented in equivalent short-term memory and long-term memory tasks.

colour and location separately. Given that each memory task has several levels (array size for short-term memory, block number and delay in long-term memory) the levels would be averaged together in the case of a non-significant group X interaction in the ANOVA or treated separately in the case of a significant interaction.

If these abilities do not co-occur, this may suggest domain specificity for perception and memory processes.

2b. Do any significant relationships between perception and memory persist when controlling for synaesthesia status and confounding variables such as age, motivation, and imagery?

The significant positive relationship between perception and memory will remain when synaesthesia status and other potential confounds (e.g., age, motivation, imagery) are included in a regression model.

As above.

Any significant correlations relating to the association between perceptual precision and memory precision (directly above) will be explored further in terms of possible confounds that might drive the association, by means of a regression model (with memory acting as dependent variable). Predictors

As above.

As above, but we could additionally interpret results in light of the contribution of motivation (i.e., if confounder, then we would interpret results as artifact of motivation/engagement levels) and imagery (i.e., if confounder, then vivid mental imagery interpreted as critically underpinning performance)

Representational accounts of cognitive processes

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will include perceptual performance (colour or location as appropriate), group status (synaesthesia coded categorically), and our other individual difference questionnaires (cognitive styles, motivation, age).

<p>3. Do individuals with grapheme-colour synaesthesia exhibit better memory and visual perceptual abilities for colour, while those with sequence-space synaesthesia demonstrate better memory and visual perceptual abilities for location when compared to each other and to non-synaesthetic controls?</p>	<p>Grapheme-colour synaesthetes will have better memory and visual perceptual abilities for colour and sequence-space synaesthetes will have better memory and visual perceptual abilities for location, in comparison to each other and non-synaesthetic controls. Individuals with both types of synaesthesia will show advantages in both tasks.</p>	<p>As above.</p> <p>ANOVA based on hypothesis one but using a 2x2 Group design based on presence/absence of grapheme colour and presence/absence of sequence space (where the 'double absent' group consist of the controls)</p>	<p>As above.</p>	<p>If visual perception is better than non-synaesthetes, and the type of synaesthesia/visual characteristics do not impact results (i.e., all synaesthetes are more accurate to remember both colours and locations), then this would support enhanced processing. If there is a specific enhancement of colour memory, this would support the ventral stream sub-theory in particular.</p> <p>If there are no performance advantages, neither dual-coding or en-</p>	<p>Dual-coding and/or enhanced processing accounts of synaesthesia</p>
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					hanced processing accounts would be supported.		
4.	Do relatives of synaesthetes display a pattern of visual perceptual ability and memory performance more similar to synaesthetes or other non-synaesthetic controls?	Relatives of synaesthetes will exhibit a similar pattern of visual perceptual ability and memory performance as the synaesthetes, albeit intermediate in magnitude. They will outperform non-synaesthetes who are not first-degree relatives of a synaesthete in the perception and memory tasks.	As above.	ANOVA with the within-subject factor Condition (colour vs. location recall) and the between-subject factor Group (synaesthetes vs. relatives vs. non-synaesthetes) and, as appropriate, the within-subject factor of array size (short-term memory) or block number (in long-term memory). Multivariate analysis and machine-learning (trained on synaesthetes vs. unrelated controls).	As above.	If relatives are more similar to synaesthetes than controls in their performance (and/or are classified as separate from unrelated controls using machine-learning techniques) this would support the view that cognitive differences in synaesthesia comprise an endophenotype.	“Synaesthetic disposition” as an endophenotype

Note. For exploratory purposes, we will repeat the above analyses including the number of types of synaesthesia (between 1 – 10) as a covariate. We do not make specific hypotheses for these exploratory analyses.

Quality Assurance: Splithalf Reliability

We assessed the quality and consistency of all dependent variables by performing split-half reliability assessments on the data using the R package splithalf (Parsons, 2021). This procedure involves randomly dividing the data into 5000 pairs. The averages of the two halves are then compared across the entire sample and the mean correlation (Spearman-Brown) for each dependent variable is reported. Whilst there are no agreed cut-offs for this measure, a higher value (> 0.8) is desired, and the lower the value the harder it is to detect effects of interest. Results from pilot testing (see Table 3 in Supplementary Materials) showed good overall reliability in our dependent variable measurement across tasks, as indicated by high Spearman-Brown coefficient values for each task and condition.

Quality Assurance: Absence of Floor and Ceiling Effects

We checked whether floor and ceiling effects were present in our data. To examine floor effects, we assessed whether performance in our most difficult tasks (the short-term memory load five condition and the long-term memory delayed recall block) was above chance. To assess ceiling effects, we assessed performance on the easiest task (visual perception) to see whether participants had perfect performance and refer to prior data on this task.

We did not observe floor or ceiling effects in our pilot test results. In the short-term memory load five task, the results of a one-sample t-test comparing mean deviations to 90 degrees ("chance", as deviation can be between 0 – 179 degrees) for location and colour were both statistically significant ($M_{\text{Location}} = 51.49$, $SD_{\text{Location}} = 13.17$, $t(5) = -7.16$, $p < 0.001$; $M_{\text{Colour}} = 61.40$, $SD_{\text{Colour}} = 9.44$, $t(5) = -7.42$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, in the long-term memory delayed recall block, the results of one-sample t-tests comparing mean deviations to 90 degrees for location and colour were both statistically significant ($M_{\text{Location}} = 24.98$, $SD_{\text{Location}} = 17.17$, $t(11) = -13.11$, $p < 0.001$; $M_{\text{Colour}} = 39.49$, $SD_{\text{Colour}} = 25.46$, $t(11) = -6.87$, $p < 0.001$). These findings indicate that mean performance is significantly different from chance in the most difficult experimental conditions and therefore an absence of floor

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effects. In the visual perception task, a one-sample t-test comparing mean deviations to 0 degrees (perfect accuracy) for location and colour were also both statistically significant ($M_{\text{Location}} = 4.25$, $SD_{\text{Location}} = 2.21$, $t(14) = 7.44$, $p < 0.001$; $M_{\text{Colour}} = 6.89$, $SD_{\text{Colour}} = 4.28$, $t(14) = 6.24$, $p < 0.001$). This shows that performance in the easiest experimental condition is not perfect and therefore an absence of ceiling effects in our task. Additionally, we note that this task has been used in the past (see Ovalle-Fresa et al, 2021) and it was suitable to detect differences on a group level.

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Table 11

Summary of Pilot Testing Design

Task	Participants	Design
Visual Perception	N = 5	Three blocks of 15 trials (45 objects).
Short-term Memory	N = 6	Three blocks of 15 trials, split according to memory load. Block one consists of 15 trials at memory load one (15 objects prompted), block two consists of 15 trials at memory load three (45 objects prompted), and block three consists of 15 trials at memory load five (75 objects prompted).
Long-term Memory (immediate recall)	N = 5	Alternating learning and testing phases (three sets of 15 objects, displayed for four repetitions each) prompted for immediate recall.
Long-term Memory (delayed recall)	N = 4	Three sets of 15 objects (as in long-term memory immediate recall above) prompted for delayed recall only 48-72 hours later. Labelled as repetition five.

Notes. All participants were recruited via Prolific and do not experience synaesthesia. Different participants completed each task, with the exception of the long-term memory task where the same participants completed both immediate and delayed recall tasks. One participant completed only the long-term memory immediate recall session, rather than both immediate recall and delayed recall.

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Table 12

Summary of Results from Pilot Testing

Task	Participants	Analysis	Results (colour)	Results (location)
Visual perception	N = 5	Summary statistics	M = 6.89, SD = 4.28	M = 4.25, SD = 2.21
		Split-half reliability: spearman-brown coefficients	SB = 0.96	SB = 0.95
Short-term memory	N = 6	Summary statistics	For load_n = 1, the mean colour deviation was M = 15.9 (SD = 5.63).	For load_n = 1, the mean location deviation was M = 12.6 (SD = 5.60).
			For load_n = 3, the mean colour deviation was M = 32.4 (SD = 12.8).	For load_n = 3, the mean location deviation was M = 21.3 (SD = 11.2).
			For load_n = 5, the mean colour deviation was M = 61.4 (SD = 9.44).	For load_n = 5, the mean location deviation was M = 51.5 (SD = 13.2).
		Pairwise t-tests	For load 1 vs. load 3, there was a significant difference in mean colour deviation (t = -2.89, df = 6.86, p = 0.02).	For load 1 vs. load 3, there was no significant difference in mean location deviation (t = -1.70, df = 7.37, p = 0.13).
For load 3 vs. load 5, here was a significant difference in mean colour deviation (t = -4.46, df = 9.19, p < 0.01).	For load 3 vs. load 5, there was a significant difference in mean location deviation (t = -4.28, df = 9.74, p < 0.01).			
		For load 1 vs. load	For load 1 vs. load	

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5, there was a significant difference in mean colour deviation ($t = -10.14$, $df = 8.16$, $p < 0.01$). 5, there was a significant difference in mean location deviation ($t = -6.65$, $df = 6.75$, $p < 0.01$).

Split-half reliability: spearman-brown coefficients

Load 1 = 0.57	Load 1 = 0.50
Load 3 = 0.87	Load 3 = 0.89
Load 5 = 0.62	Load 5 = 0.83

Long-term memory (immediate recall)	N = 5	Summary statistics	For block 1, $M = 65.2$, $SD = 51.2$	For block 1, $M = 49.1$, $SD = 44.9$
			For the final block of immediate recall (4), $M = 36.1$, $SD = 33.2$	For the final block of immediate recall (4), $M = 15.8$, $SD = 16.1$

Pairwise t-test

There was a significant difference in mean colour deviation between the first and last blocks ($t = 3.12$, $df = 27.65$, $p < 0.01$). This is indicative of learning across blocks.	There was a significant difference in mean location deviation between the first and last blocks ($t = 4.60$, $df = 19.70$, $p < 0.01$). This is indicative of learning across blocks.
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Split-half reliability: spearman-brown coefficients

Block 1 = 0.93	Block 1 = 0.94
Final block (4) = 0.94	Final block (4) = 0.96

Long-term memory (delayed recall)	N = 4	Summary statistics	For the delayed recall block (5), $M = 39.5$, $SD = 32.1$	For the delayed recall block (5), $M = 25.0$, $SD = 31.1$
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Pairwise t-test

There was a significant difference	There was a significant difference
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	<p>in mean colour deviation between the first block of the long-term memory immediate task and the delayed recall block (5) ($t = 2.54$, $df = 24.26$, $p = 0.02$).</p> <p>No significant differences were observed between the delayed recall block and any other pairwise comparison (i.e., repetitions 2-4, all $p > 0.05$). This is indicative of remembering.</p>	<p>in mean location deviation between the first block of the long-term memory immediate task and the delayed recall block (5) ($t = 2.93$, $df = 24.40$, $p < 0.01$).</p> <p>No significant differences were observed between the delayed recall block and any other pairwise comparison (i.e., repetitions 2-4, all $p > 0.05$). This is indicative of remembering.</p>
Split-half reliability: spearman-brown coefficients	Delayed recall block (5) = 0.97	Delayed recall block (5) = 0.88

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Figure 1

Density Plots of Results from Visual Perception Task Pilot, by Condition.

Note. In the density plots, values closer to 0 indicate more precise recall. Participants are accurate overall but do not show a ceiling effect (i.e. not all responses are at zero).

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Figure 2

Line graphs showing results from the short-term memory task pilot, by condition

Note. Each participant is referred to by a unique identifier (e.g., P01) and the black line represents the group mean at each load.

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Figure 3

Density plots showing results from the short-term memory task pilot, by condition

Note. In the density plots, values closer to 0 indicate more precise recall.

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Figure 4

Line graphs showing results from the long-term memory task pilot, by condition

Note. IR = immediate recall and DR = delayed recall. Each participant is referred to by a unique identifier (e.g., P01) and the black line represents the group mean at each load.

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Table 13

Robustness of Confirmatory Results to Session-Duration Exclusion Criteria: Visual Perception Task

Exclusion criterion	N excluded (total / task)	Hypothesis 1: Syns vs. Cons		Hypothesis 3: GCS main effect		Hypothesis: 3 SSS main effect		Hypothesis 3: GCS × SSS interaction		Hypothesis 4: Syns vs. Rels vs. Cons	
		Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 2	.1762 / < .001*	.1367 / < .001*	.1220 / < .001*	.0563 / < .001*	.0265 / .019*	.0540 / < .001*	.0716 / < .001*	.0447 / .002*	.2833 / < .001*	.2287 / < .001*
Main (½ × median)	24 / 15	.1602 / < .001*	.1449 / < .001*	.1141 / < .001*	.0575 / < .001*	.0182 / .059	.0456 / .002*	.0756 / < .001*	.0496 / .002*	.2597 / < .001*	.2077 / < .001*
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 92	.1161 / < .001*	.0809 / < .001*	.0814 / < .001*	.0262 / .049*	.0115 / .192	.0714 / .001*	.0631 / .002*	.0096 / .234	.2093 / < .001*	.1600 / < .001*
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 110	.1060 / < .001*	.1167 / < .001*	.0642 / .003*	.0342 / .029*	.0101 / .244	.0752 / .001*	.0722 / .002*	.0180 / .115	.1912 / < .001*	.1489 / < .001*

Note. N excluded (total / task) = cumulative exclusions across all criteria / exclusions attributable to the session-duration threshold for this task. GCS = grapheme-colour synaesthesia; SSS = sequence-space synaesthesia. Values are presented as η^2p / p . The main confirmatory criterion (½ × median) is shown in bold. * $p < .05$.

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Table 14

Robustness of Confirmatory Results to Session-Duration Exclusion Criteria: Short-Term Memory (STM) Task

Exclusion criterion	N excluded (total / task)	Hypothesis 1: Syns vs. Cons		Hypothesis 3: GCS main effect		Hypothesis 3: SSS main effect		Hypothesis 3: GCS × SSS interaction		Hypothesis 4: Syns vs. Rels vs. Cons	
		Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location
Load 1											
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 1	.0789* / < .001	.0416* / .003	.1056* / < .001	.0080 / .203	.0009 / .671	.0173 / .060	.0125 / .110	.0067 / .244	.1870* / < .001	.0366* / .005
Main (½ × median)	24 / 5	.0788* / < .001	.0430* / .003	.1052* / < .001	.0084 / .191	.0009 / .675	.0179 / .057	.0125 / .112	.0070 / .235	.1622* / < .001	.0342* / .009
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 39	.0772* / < .001	.0548* / .001	.1149* / < .001	.0163 / .088	.0009 / .687	.0249* / .034	.0109 / .160	.0185 / .069	.1503* / < .001	.0485* / .002
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 54	.0860* / < .001	.0530* / .002	.1236* / < .001	.0201 / .064	.0027 / .495	.0181 / .079	.0167 / .091	.0160 / .099	.1547* / < .001	.0502* / .003
Load 3											
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 1	.0235* / .025	.0292* / .013	.0492* / .001	.0298* / .013	.0016 / .568	.0016 / .564	.0061 / .266	.0139 / .091	.0229* / .037	.0507* / < .001
Main (½ × median)	24 / 5	.0243* / .024	.0307* / .011	.0526* / .001	.0310* / .011	.0009 / .669	.0018 / .540	.0070 / .233	.0144 / .086	.0267* / .024	.0515* / < .001
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 39	.0282* / .021	.0335* / .012	.0608* / < .001	.0303* / .019	.0012 / .638	.0053 / .329	.0057 / .313	.0231* / .041	.0372* / .009	.0438* / .004
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 54	.0259* / .032	.0311* / .019	.0701* / < .001	.0335* / .017	.0022 / .544	.0025 / .516	.0059 / .322	.0232* / .047	.0412* / .008	.0387* / .011
Load 5											
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 1	.0117 / .117	.0025 / .471	.0209* / .036	.0027 / .454	.0017 / .554	.0001 / .918	.0030 / .428	.0049 / .316	.0468* / .001	.0647* / < .001
Main (½ × median)	24 / 5	.0120 / .112	.0029 / .438	.0213* / .035	.0030 / .430	.0016 / .564	.0000 / .941	.0031 / .423	.0051 / .305	.0348* / .007	.0501* / < .001
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 39	.0109 / .153	.0080 / .224	.0227* / .040	.0073 / .249	.0029 / .469	.0000 / .955	.0033 / .436	.0090 / .199	.0224 / .057	.0385* / .007
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 54	.0111 / .163	.0058 / .314	.0203 / .060	.0046 / .372	.0022 / .536	.0000 / .967	.0042 / .393	.0104 / .182	.0211 / .079	.0318* / .022

Note. N excluded (total / task) = cumulative exclusions across all criteria / exclusions attributable to the session-duration threshold for this task. GCS = grapheme-colour synaesthesia; SSS = sequence-space synaesthesia. Values are presented as η^2p / p . The main confirmatory criterion (½ × median) is shown in bold. * $p < .05$.

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Table 15

Robustness of Confirmatory Results to Session-Duration Exclusion Criteria: Long-Term Memory Immediate Recall Task

Exclusion criterion	N excluded (total/task)	Hypothesis 1: Syns vs. Cons		Hypothesis 3: GCS main effect		Hypothesis 3: SSS main effect		Hypothesis 3: GCS × SSS interaction		Hypothesis 4: Syns vs. Rels vs. Cons	
		Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 4	.0388 / .004*	.0515 / < .001*	.1006 / < .001*	.0208 / .035*	.0000 / .947	.0069 / .227	.0019 / .529	.0207 / .036*	.0989 / < .001*	.0425 / .002*
Main (½ × median)	24 / 4	.0388 / .004*	.0515 / < .001*	.1006 / < .001*	.0208 / .035*	.0000 / .947	.0069 / .227	.0019 / .529	.0207 / .036*	.0914 / < .001*	.0429 / .002*
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 25	.0175 / .061	.0275 / .019*	.0837 / < .001*	.0087 / .187	.0028 / .465	.0019 / .537	.0001 / .868	.0156 / .077	.0972 / < .001*	.0273 / .024*
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 4	.0388 / .004*	.0515 / < .001*	.1006 / < .001*	.0208 / .035*	.0000 / .947	.0069 / .227	.0019 / .529	.0207 / .036*	.0989 / < .001*	.0425 / .002*

Note. N excluded (total / task) = cumulative exclusions across all criteria / exclusions attributable to the session-duration threshold for this task. GCS = grapheme-colour synaesthesia; SSS = sequence-space synaesthesia. Values are presented as η^2p / p . The main confirmatory criterion (½ × median) is shown in bold. * $p < .05$.

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Table 16

Robustness of Confirmatory Results to Session-Duration Exclusion Criteria: Long-Term Memory Delayed Task

Exclusion criterion	N excluded (total/task)	Hypothesis 1: Syns vs. Cons		Hypothesis 3: GCS main effect		Hypothesis 3: SSS main effect		Hypothesis 3: GCS × SSS interaction		Hypothesis 4: Syns vs. Rels vs. Cons	
		Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location	Colour	Location
Lenient (½ × 25th percentile)	7 / 2	.0216 / .033*	.0132 / .100	.0579 / <.001*	.0115 / .127	.0068 / .238	.0009 / .674	.0008 / .694	.0138 / .094	.0565 / <.001*	.0100 / .244
Main (½ × median)	24 / 15	.0216 / .038*	.0148 / .088	.0656 / <.001*	.0139 / .100	.0114 / .135	.0016 / .577	.0014 / .594	.0164 / .075	.0531 / <.001*	.0108 / .239
Strict (½ × 75th percentile)	156 / 92	.0183 / .096	.0110 / .200	.0893 / <.001*	.0213 / .074	.0330 / .025*	.0156 / .128	.0005 / .790	.0099 / .225	.0802 / <.001*	.0203 / .130
Original criterion (< 30 min)	168 / 110	.0101 / .235	.0009 / .733	.0878 / <.001*	.0111 / .222	.0444 / .013*	.0364 / .026*	.0000 / .974	.0040 / .463	.0653 / .002*	.0180 / .195

Note. *N* excluded (total / task) = cumulative exclusions across all criteria / exclusions attributable to the session-duration threshold for this task. GCS = grapheme-colour synaesthesia; SSS = sequence-space synaesthesia. Values are presented as η^2p / p . The main confirmatory criterion (½ × median) is shown in bold. * $p < .05$.